

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

Final Report (December 02, 2025)

by

Maurice Jones, Marek Blottière, Philippe Pasquier, Ola Siebert,
Fenwick McKelvey, Nathalie Casemajor, Klara Mahoas, and Pía
Baltazar

SOCIÉTÉ DES ARTS
TECHNOLOGIQUES

Table of Contents

0. Executive Summary	3
Who Is This Report For?.....	3
How to Read?.....	3
Context and Rationale.....	4
Key Challenges across Themes.....	5
Key Recommendations.....	8
Project Proposals.....	10
1. Introduction	13
2. Imagining a Commons	17
What Is a “Commons?”.....	17
Digital Commons and the Paradox of Open.....	18
AI Commons.....	19
Artistic, Creative, and Cultural AI Countergovernance.....	21
Case Studies.....	23
Commons, Cooperativism, and AI in Québec and Canada.....	24
Cultural Commons in Québec and Canada.....	25
AI and Tech Cooperativism in Canada.....	26
3. A Methodology for Commoning	28
May–Oct 2024 Phase 1: Collective and Iterative Situational Mapping.....	28
Nov 2024–Apr 2025 Phase 2: In-person Consultations.....	30
1st ArtIA Symposium.....	30
2nd ArtIA Symposium.....	32
Apr–Aug 2025 Phase 3: Publication.....	34
3rd ArtIA Symposium.....	34
4. Prototyping an AI Commons	36
Disciplinary Working Groups: On the Arts, For the Arts, In the Arts.....	38
Social Sciences & Humanities.....	39
Technology.....	40
Research–Creation.....	41
Interdisciplinary Thematic Clusters.....	42
Accessibility & Education.....	44
Artistic Practices.....	46
Data.....	48
Communities & Publics.....	50

- Governance & Industry Relations..... 52
- Tools & Infrastructures..... 55
- Sustainability..... 57
- Project Proposals.....58
- 5. Intermezzo: Reimagining a Commons for AI in Digital Creation..... 62**
- 6. Building a Commons..... 66**
 - Small Data and Model Crafting: Artisanal AI Tools, Methods, and Practices..... 66
 - Community Consultations, Shared Concerns..... 66
 - Objectives..... 67
 - Roadmap..... 68
 - Stakeholders and Governance..... 68
 - ArtIA Summer School: A Knowledge Commons for Creative AI..... 69
 - Community Consultations, Shared Concerns..... 69
 - Objectives..... 70
 - Roadmap..... 70
 - Stakeholders and Governance..... 71
 - Sovereign Compute: Developing Common Infrastructures for AI in Digital Creation..... 73
 - Community Consultations, Shared Concerns..... 73
 - Objectives..... 74
 - Roadmap..... 74
 - Stakeholders and Governance..... 75
- 7. Conclusion..... 76**
 - Key Recommendations..... 76
 - In Moving Forward..... 78
- 8. References..... 81**
- 9. Appendix..... 88**

O. Executive Summary

Who Is This Report For?

This report is intended for artists, creatives, cultural organizations, researchers, policymakers, technologists, and industry players interested in shaping ethical, inclusive, and sustainable approaches to artificial intelligence in the arts and the cultural and creative sectors in Québec, Canada, and beyond. It addresses both those already engaged in AI-related initiatives in the arts, the cultural sector, government, and industry, as well as newcomers seeking to understand how an AI commons for digital creation rooted in shared practices and infrastructures can serve artistic creation, the sustainability of the cultural and creative sectors, and the broader public interest in Québec and Canada.

How to Read?

This report captures the results of an 18-month process of stakeholder consultation, collective research, and co-creation exploring the possibility of building an AI commons for digital creation in the arts in Québec and Canada. It can be read either as a continuous narrative or by section, depending on the reader's needs:

1. **Context and Rationale:** The *Introduction* outlines the motivations behind the project, explaining why AI, why commons, why digital creation, and why the Québec and Canadian context are central to this initiative.
2. **Literature and Conceptual Foundations:** Section 2 *Imagining* reviews the diverse histories, concepts, and models of commoning. In situating the project, particular attention is paid to recent advancements in the realm of cultural, creative, digital, and AI commons and to their intersections with approaches rooted in postcolonial, Indigenous, and other critical approaches.
3. **Methodology:** Section 3 *Methodology* describes the participatory approach to stakeholder consultations, which, beyond merely asking for opinions, enrolled participants in co-creating a collective vision for an AI commons. Methods ranged from situational mapping and interviews to workshops and symposia. The section further details who was involved and how.

4. **Key Learnings and Thematic Analysis:** Section 4 *Prototyping* combines storytelling and thematic synthesis to present the main insights generated across disciplinary working groups and interdisciplinary and thematic working groups, which led to 20 concrete project proposals and a collective vision of a possible commons for AI in digital creation.
5. **Project Proposals and Prototyping:** Section 5 *Building* presents three concrete initiatives developed during the process on small data and model crafting, education and training, and sovereign compute. These proposals include reasoning and roadmaps alongside governance proposals, advocacy strategies, partnership models, and funding pathways.
6. **Conclusion and Next Steps:** Summarizes strategic priorities, timelines, and next steps to guide the development of an AI commons for the arts and cultural institutions.

Context and Rationale

In summer 2024, the Canadian government launched a public consultation on Canadian Sovereign AI Compute Strategy. Published in May 2025, the government pledged \$2 billion to support researchers and tech corporations in ensuring Canada’s competitiveness in the global AI race. None of these funds are allocated to the arts and cultural organizations. While the Canadian government consulted on sovereign compute in 2024, a network of Québec cultural organizations began gathering around shared concerns about the dominance of industrial policy for AI that favours tech corporations, sidelining the arts and culture and positioning them merely as downstream adopters of innovative technologies. Under the umbrella of *ArtIA: Towards a Commons for AI in Digital Creation*, artists and cultural workers came together to advance a commons-based alternative to the dominant AI paradigm—an approach rooted in collective ownership, cooperative infrastructures, and creative reappropriation.

Rather than framing the debate around whether a commons is needed, the central question is what kind of governance, tools, and infrastructures can safeguard cultural labour against extractive business models while strengthening cultural ecosystems. ArtIA situates this debate within Québec and Canada’s unique context. In particular, Montréal and Toronto have emerged as global AI hubs, hosting major tech companies, world-class research institutions, as well as pioneering debates surrounding ethical and responsible AI. Home to a thriving digital creative sector, Québec is well positioned to advance critical discussions about the impacts of AI on the arts and cultural sectors. Lastly, Québec and Canada host longstanding traditions of mutual aid, cooperative enterprise, and cultural

sovereignty—enriched by Indigenous, francophone, and immigrant practices—that provide strong foundations for experimentation in shared governance.

While fraught with challenges, the Québec and Canadian context presented ample opportunities to launch an inclusive and equitable stakeholder consultation to explore the possibilities of a commons for AI in digital creation.

Key Challenges across Themes

Over the course of 18 months, the stakeholder consultations identified seven central themes to be considered in shaping the development and integration of AI in the arts and cultural sectors.

These themes served as a framework for mapping the most pressing challenges faced by artists, cultural organizations, and communities engaging with AI. They provide a lens to understand not only technical and artistic issues but also the ethical, social, and environmental dimensions of building an AI commons for the arts.

Theme	Key Challenges
Accessibility & Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Fostering critical and ethical AI literacy: Curricula that equip artists to interrogate the application of AI in and through artistic practice, within cultural organizations with particular attention towards dominant narratives and algorithmic power dynamics.● Ensuring accessibility and inclusivity: Hardware access, adaptable learning styles, and safe spaces for artists, cultural workers, and underrepresented communities, supported by diverse modes of engagement.● Creativity- and culture-centred pedagogy: Position AI as a medium for artistic and cultural experimentation, not an end in itself.

<p>Artistic Practices</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Artistic autonomy: Preserve artistic, creative, and cultural autonomy when working with AI. ● Creative and cultural pluralism: Safeguard diversity in artistic and cultural practices by embedding ethical reflection and resisting the homogenization of creative production in the application of AI. ● Sustainable practices: Ensure the sustainability and adaptability of artistic tools and practices. ● Cultural R&D: Reposition artistic practice as a central force in cultural research and development (R&D). ● Interdisciplinary collaboration: Foster interdisciplinary collaboration instead of individualized interactions with AI systems.
<p>Data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Ethical data sovereignty: Ensure artists retain control, privacy, and consent over their data through community-defined governance, while supporting small-data tools that enable context-specific, customizable, and ethical use. ● Diversity, inclusion, and accessibility: Datasets must reflect underrepresented art forms, geographic diversity, and be openly accessible with sustainable archiving. ● Data quality and ethics: Concerns included lack of accuracy, insufficient documentation, cultural insensitivity, privacy risks, and limited transparency.
<p>Communities & Publics</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Community-aligned development: Strengthen existing artistic communities by co-creating AI tools that reflect their values, support governance, and address their specific needs. ● Building bridges between communities: The potential of an AI commons as connective infrastructures to foster dialogue and collaboration among diverse communities and between communities and the broader public. ● Empowering community-centred organizations: Support and empower existing organizations like libraries to act as digital commons that enhance

	<p>access, foster discoverability, and facilitate artist-controlled data trusts for data sovereignty and creative autonomy.</p>
<p>Governance & Industry Relations</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Define the creative AI commons and its stewardship through noncommercial, community-based governance models that ensure artists retain control over data and gain access to resources and knowledge inspired by established cases, such as public libraries and cooperative governance. ● Establish artist-centric governance to address power imbalances with industry by promoting fair representation, bottom-up structures, and collective negotiation. ● Develop new legal and economic frameworks such as data trusts, universal basic income (UBI), and legal clinics to support fair compensation and intellectual property protection in AI-driven arts. ● Negotiating with industry: Advance community-driven strategies like collective bargaining and alternative ownership models to empower artists and challenge tech monopolies.
<p>Tools & Infrastructures</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Access is not an afterthought: Artists face steep hardware costs and steep learning curves. The group emphasized clear tutorials, low-tech on-ramps, and no-code interfaces (with direct manipulation where possible) to bridge the gap. ● Ethics in the kernel: Dataset transparency, data sovereignty, and anti-censorship defaults were deemed nonnegotiable. Local compute and community-run platforms offer the strongest guarantees. ● Small data and model crafting: Empower artists to use their own data and craft custom models, taking control of the full production chain. Small data approaches also offer eco-friendly tactics to reduce AI art’s carbon footprint. ● Mutualization and resource sharing: Sharing technologies and resources can improve access and reduce redundancy but raises coordination

	<p>challenges—especially when partnering with institutions that may conflict with the community’s values. Clear strategies are needed to navigate these tensions.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Centralised vs distributed: Participants debated a single hub against a mesh of nodes; resilience and self-governance tipped the scales towards the latter. ● Infrastructures = hardware + people: Governance models, access policies, and recognition protocols matter as much as silicon. The group identified a need for the entire production chain to become a commons.
<p>Sustainability</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Thinking long-term: Integrate consideration of environmental, social, and technological impacts into the design of AI projects. ● Decentralization and resource sharing: Promote local, shared, and accessible infrastructures to strengthen community autonomy. ● Solidarity and ethical respect: Anchor projects in principles of social justice, transparency, and respect for all living beings. ● Bridging knowledge and fostering collaborations: Encourage unlikely alliances and highlight community-based expertise, notably Indigenous knowledge. ● Collective maintenance and long-term sustainability: Organize the upkeep of systems and build living networks of skills and competencies to ensure their lasting evolution.

Key Recommendations

To ensure that the cultural sector can harness AI technologies without losing autonomy, value, or cultural specificity, a proactive strategy must be adopted. While AI raises legitimate concerns, ranging from ethical risks to potential loss of control over data and creative processes, the cultural sector in Québec and Canada itself is also in a moment of fragility. Economic pressures, rapid technological shifts, and evolving audience expectations mean it must simultaneously reinvent itself and be supported through this transition.

Given the fundamental differences between the economic objectives of most technology companies and the missions pursued by artists and the cultural sector the following actions are recommended:

Recommendations	Intended Impact
Invest in Dedicated Compute Infrastructures	Ensure long-term access to AI tools and resources governed by collective, nonextractive models.
Strengthen Sector Expertise	Equip organizations and artists with the technical, legal, and strategic skills to appropriate AI ethically and effectively.
Establish Localized AI Labs	Provide communities with spaces for R&D, experimentation, and direct access to AI infrastructures, expertise, and tools.
Adjust Funding Programs	Adjust municipal, provincial, and federal funding programs across the arts and academic sectors to allow for the development of critical infrastructures and intersectorial collaboration.
Accelerate Technological Catch-Up	Reduce the digital divide by helping artists and cultural organizations rapidly adopt and adapt homegrown AI technologies.
Promote Knowledge Sharing and Transferability	Ensure that findings and innovations are documented, accessible, and beneficial across the sector.
Forge Cross-Sector Partnerships	Foster stronger collaboration among artistic communities, cultural institutions, technology providers, academic researchers, and policymakers.

Project Proposals

Throughout the ArtIA symposia and workshops, participants not only identified pressing challenges but also demonstrated remarkable creativity and initiative in proposing solutions. Participants generated 20 concrete project ideas that address thematic challenges and begin to implement of the seven key recommendations.

Embracing a proactive approach, several projects have already been launched. These include the creation of an open knowledge base with partner Projet Collectif,¹ the production of a series of podcasts critically investigating the application of AI in digital creation in collaboration with the IANF Research Chair,² and the co-development of glossaries defining and summarizing critical terminology surrounding AI in the arts and cultural sectors between OBVIA and the ArtIA Consortium.³

Most importantly, three large-scale pilot projects have been prioritized for development. Together, they cover the core pillars identified as essential for building an AI commons for digital creation in Québec and Canada. These pillars target the development of **artist-centred tools, critical learning resources, and shared compute infrastructures.**

¹ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/cn/>

² See <https://chaireianf.ca/balado-ianf/>

³ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/cn/pbQ77OtAFkIXcV5aBfAkYOG1TYw/>

Project	Focus	Purpose & Vision	Status	Potential partners
<p>Small Data & Model Crafting <i>(Artisanal AI Tools, Methods, and Practices)</i></p>	<p>Software Tools</p>	<p>Objective 1: Create a modular, open-source, artist-friendly AI toolkit prioritizing small data, local computation, and creative sovereignty. Resist big-data dependency, cloud lock-in, and opaque systems by providing accessible GUIs, model crafting capabilities, and open governance.</p> <p>Objective 2: Develop artistic research-creation case studies as a practical feedback mechanism.</p>	<p>Both Objective 1 (Tool Development, NSERC Alliance Society, PI: Pasquier) and Objective 2 (Research-Creation Study, SSHRC Insight, PI: Vigliensoni) are in proposal development, with applications being written during this report's compilation and targeted for submission in Fall 2025.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Simon Fraser University ● Concordia University ● Université de Montréal ● ArtIA ● MUTEK ● Sporobole ● VIVO
<p>ArtIA Summer School <i>(A Knowledge Commons for Creative AI)</i></p>	<p>Critical Learning Resources</p>	<p>Establish an interdisciplinary, artist-focused training program that integrates technical skills with critical AI literacy, inclusive pedagogy, and playful formats. Build a "living laboratory" for co-learning between artists, researchers, and cultural organizations.</p>	<p>The training department at the Society for Arts and Technology (SAT) is currently developing the frame of the pilot project Summer School. Partners and funding will be sought in Fall 2025. The pilot project will be</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● SAT ● NAD ● Hexagram ● a CCTT (such as CDRIN) ● Pôle Synthèse ● MUTEK

			implemented in Summer 2026.	
<p>Sovereign Compute Infrastructures <i>(Developing Common Infrastructures for AI in Digital Creation)</i></p>	<p>Compute Infra-structures</p>	<p>Build a peer-governed, artist-friendly computing infrastructures by mapping existing resources, developing equitable sharing frameworks, and piloting collaborative GPU clusters to ensure long-term technological sovereignty for the cultural sector.</p>	<p>Participants and cultural organizations are currently gathering as an informal pilot network exploring how to share existing compute infrastructures.</p> <p>At the same time, the network is lobbying Compute Canada/Calcul Québec, as well as the Canadian government in light of the Sovereign AI Compute Strategy.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sporobole • SAT • Calcul Québec • PINQ2

1. Introduction

In response to a recent manifesto by Québec cultural organizations expressing powerlessness in the face of AI, artists and cultural workers at the digital arts center Sporobole in Sherbrooke proposed an alternative path: concrete, transferable solutions grounded in collective ownership and creative reappropriation. Instead of retreating into nostalgia or fear, this perspective urges artists and cultural cooperatives in digital creation to engage AI on their own terms—developing shared tools, mutual aid, and resilient infrastructures that strengthen rather than deplete cultural ecosystems.

Artists and cultural workers in digital creation are the canaries in the coal mine of big AI's hegemonic absorption of cultural labour—an effect of the paradox of the commons, where openness and sharing, foundational to the digital commons, fuel both exploitation and innovation (Peszowska, 2024). Trained on massive public data sets and embedded in the next-generation business logics of platforms (Van Der Vlist et al., 2024), generative AI destabilizes established informal knowledge commons and their governance norms. Rather than asking whether a commons for AI is needed, we ask what kind of commons we want.

ArtIA: Towards a Commons for AI in Digital Creation explores these questions from the specific standpoint of digital creation in Québec and Canada. According to the Canada Council for the Arts, Canada supports vibrant and diverse artistic communities across the country, with cities such as Montréal, Toronto, Vancouver, and Ottawa internationally recognized for their dynamic creative scenes. In 2023 alone, the Canada Council for the Arts sponsored 1,125 projects, providing grants totaling \$36.2 million and supporting thousands of artists and cultural workers. The Canadian artistic landscape is enriched by its tremendous cultural diversity, including Indigenous artists and creators from a wide range of cultural backgrounds. The arts and culture sector generates billions of dollars and provides numerous jobs, playing a vital role in the Canadian economy. Québec stands out as a province with greater autonomy, which allows it to pursue distinct initiatives and foster innovation, particularly in the digital arts sector, leading to a broader impact (Smith & Couture Gagnon, 2024; Wehbe, 2024). As the only solely francophone province in North America, Québec's linguistic and cultural distinctiveness has long shaped its approach to both technological development and cultural policy.

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

Québec and Canada are leaders both in the technological development and the ethical and responsible governance of AI. In particular, Montréal and Toronto have emerged as global AI hubs, hosting major tech companies and research institutions supported by a robust research and innovation ecosystem anchored around institutions, such as Mila – Québec Artificial Intelligence Institute and the Vector Institute. Tech giants such as Meta, Google, and Microsoft have established strong footholds in Québec and Canada, often partnering with local universities and research centers (Montréal International, 2024). At the same time, Québec boasts a thriving digital creative sector, contributing \$1.2 billion annually to the provincial economy. Despite this deep interconnection between technology and culture, the role and impact of AI in the cultural sector, creative industries, and digital arts remain largely undefined. Public discourse tends to focus narrowly on content generation and discoverability, copyright, and creative ownership, overlooking critical issues of redistribution, recognition, and artistic relevance.

Québec and Canada offer a fertile context for exploring a commons for AI in digital creation due to their deep-rooted traditions of mutual aid, cooperative enterprise, and collective stewardship, shaped by Indigenous knowledge systems, settler cooperativism, and immigrant community practices. This legacy is sustained today through thousands of cooperatives across sectors and robust cultural commons infrastructures, particularly in Québec, where francophone identity, aspirations for cultural sovereignty, and social economy institutions foster experimentation in shared governance and cultural production.⁴ A growing network of Canadian and Québec tech co-ops—such as Hypha Worker Co-operative, Communautique, and Percolab Coop—are adapting cooperative principles to digital infrastructures, AI, and open-source development, embedding values of equity, transparency, and solidarity into technological design (Lechat & Jay, 2023). This constitutes the context within which *ArtIA: Towards a Commons for AI in Digital Creation* explores fostering responsible, sustainable innovation that directly supports the needs and realities of the arts and cultural sectors in Québec and Canada.

This report presents the findings of the first phase of *ArtIA: Towards a Commons for AI in Digital Creation*, a distributed, community-driven initiative focused on exploring and shaping the role of AI in digital creation through the lens of the cultural commons. Led by a core partnership—the Society for Arts and Technology, Sporobole, and Projet Collectif—ArtIA conducted a 18-month stakeholder

⁴ Several organizations in Canada exemplify such cooperative structures, including Canada.coop, École nationale d'administration publique [ENAP], Fédération des coopératives du Nouveau-Québec [FCNQ], and Réseau Coopsco.

consultation from April 2024 to August 2025. This process brought together artists, creatives, cultural workers, researchers, technologists, cultural organizations, tech cooperatives, government bodies, and university research labs to assess the challenges and opportunities AI poses to digital creation in Québec and Canada. Centring the voices of artists and cultural workers, the consultation created grassroots spaces to articulate sector needs, envision a potential AI commons, and develop a concrete action plan to realize that vision—offering an alternative to the dominant sociotechnical paradigms shaped by Silicon Valley. This plan of action is set to be implemented as phase 2 of ArtIA.

Figure 1. Workplan of the ArtIA consortium.

The following chapters trace the work accomplished by ArtIA in the last 18 months. In setting the table, Chapter 2 presents both theoretical and practical explorations of the commons with a particular focus on culture and technology as well as creation and AI. It contextualizes our work within theoretical discussions as well as in relation to concrete digital and AI commons initiatives in North America, Europe, and the global majority world. Chapter 3 outlines the participatory research methodology that facilitated stakeholder engagement in generating bottom-up insights about the challenges and opportunities regarding the impact of AI on digital creation, as well as needs and wants regarding a potential AI commons.

These insights are synthesized in Chapter 4, the core of this report. It draws on findings from expert interviews, collective workshops, and three participatory research symposia held in November 2024,

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

April 2025, and August 2025. The chapter traces how ArtIA transitioned from three disciplinary working groups—Social Sciences & Humanities, Technology, and Research–Creation—towards interdisciplinary groups organized around shared concerns: Accessibility & Education, Artistic Practices, Data, Communities & Publics, Governance & Industry Relations, Tools & Infrastructures, and Sustainability. These thematic explorations helped shape a collective vision for an AI commons in digital creation, while also generating 20 concrete project proposals aimed at realizing that vision, as presented at the end of the chapter.

Chapter 5 presents three high-priority projects that participants chose to develop further: Small Data and Model Crafting, ArtIA Summer School, and Sovereign Compute Infrastructures. These project proposals, some of which are already in development, are framed by their reasoning, concrete objectives, implementation roadmaps, and potential partnerships. The conclusion summarizes the project's key findings, relates these to the questions raised at the beginning of this report, presents a roadmap, and issues a call to action for establishing a Commons for AI in Digital Creation.

This report and research project are a highly collaborative effort. Key contributors in writing were Maurice Jones, Marek Blottière, Philippe Pasquier, Ola Siebert, Klara Mahoas, Pía Baltazar, Fenwick McKelvey, Bart Simon, Arshia Sobhan, Marc-Olivier Ducharme, Éric Desmarais, Nathalie Casemajor, and Étienne Grenier. The report is made possible by the extensive documentation provided by project partner *Projet Collectif*, in particular the work by Jacinthe Jacques, Frédérique Dubé, and Alice Rivard. The implementation of the first two symposia was supported by Julie Desjardins and Stéphane Dubé of *LLio - Le Laboratoire en innovation ouverte*. The Machine Agencies research group at Concordia University supported the proofreading and editing of this report with the contribution of Rob Hunt. Lastly, credit goes to the participants—the artists, creatives, cultural workers, bureaucrats, researchers, and technologists who participated in the expert interviews, participatory workshops, roundtables, and symposia—without whom this collective research and creation endeavour would not have been possible (for a list of participants, please see Appendix IV). ArtIA is made possible by the financial assistance provided by the *Gouvernement du Québec* and the *Conseil des arts et des lettres du Québec (CALQ)*.

2. Imagining a Commons

Misconceptions of the commons are common. AI talk so often mentions common matters that we are at pains to detail what exactly the commons means to AI. The turn towards ethical and responsible AI in corporate and government strategy has framed AI as a common good (Green, 2021; Jobin et al., 2019; Stark et al., 2021). AI's probabilistic outputs—specifically in applications based on large language models—approximate common sense by generating the most likely word (or token) associations (Bauer & Schiele, 2024; Brachman & Levesque, 2023). Even as AI becomes a common feature, embedded in operating systems and devices, the growing power of AI firms (MAANGO for Microsoft, Apple, Amazon, Nvidia, Google, and OpenAI) has prompted debates in parliaments—houses of commons— over regulating AI. Some have called for AI to become a public utility—something like an infrastructure or common carrier for a new generation of information services (Dyer-Witthford et al., 2019; Ferrari, 2024). After all, some AI systems are trained on the Common Crawl archive of the Internet (Baack, 2024; Baio, 2024). What we are faced with here is a confusing if not misdirecting muddle of commons thinking, which is on its way to becoming another buzzword. Yet, rather than throw out the baby, ArtIA aims to develop a commons theory that responds to the concrete needs and challenges facing the cultural sector in Québec and presents a basis for cross-sectoral collective action in both the regulatory and the practice space.

What Is a “Commons?”

The commons is a multifaceted and contested concept spanning diverse intellectual traditions, from Public Choice Theory to Autonomous Marxism, and can be approached through conceptual, procedural, historic, and normative lenses (Harney & Moten, 2013; Hess & Ostrom, 2006; Martin, 2013). At its most basic, it refers to “common provisions or resources” (Oxford English Dictionary, 2024). While Garrett Hardin’s infamous “tragedy of the commons” framed it narrowly as a property management issue rooted in racist and eugenicist logics (Braman, 2012; Chávez-García, 2023), Elinor Ostrom’s work reframed the discussion, shifting focus from what the commons is to how it is governed (Ostrom, 2000, 2012). Her research into heterogeneous models of common-pool resource governance, from fisheries to aerospace to AI, emphasized collective management through varied institutional arrangements (Disco & Kranakis, 2013; Johnson, 2022). Yet, despite integrating examples from both settler colonial and precolonial contexts, Ostrom’s framework remained anchored in Western political-economic notions of the commons as a resource-pool, a perspective that continues to

dominate discourse. Complementing this, Paul Gilroy and Peter Linebaugh's rearticulations of Atlantic history illuminate how enclosures in Ireland propelled colonial expansion, producing varied relationships to the commons (Gilroy, 2003; Linebaugh, 2014). For Linebaugh (2021, pp. 9–10), the commons is not only a governance model but a situated way of life predating industrial capitalism, rooted in mutuality and collective existence, with enduring "fugitive" forms persisting in marginalized communities today (Tsing, 2021).

Alongside these historical and political-economic understandings, the commons also carries a radical and utopian dimension. This tradition, described by Linebaugh (2021, p. 10) as the "American commons," is marked by a productive ambivalence—neither wholly real nor wholly imaginary—shaped by European fantasies, fears, and encounters with Indigenous peoples and famously imagined in Thomas More's *Utopia*. Building on these historical roots, posthumanist thinkers engage the commons as a framework for envisioning future multispecies relations (Singh, 2017; Tola, 2015). For Dimitris Papadopoulos (2010, p. 148), the "eco-commons" entails building interconnected alternative forms of life capable of accommodating the multiplicity of hybrid entities generated by contemporary technoscience and global capitalism—a vision that could extend toward a multi-agentic commons involving AI. In this way, the commons emerges not only as a contested political-economic construct but also as a lived practice and a normative horizon for reimagining collective life beyond the human.

Digital Commons and the Paradox of Open

The commons is a central concept to the internet and digitality, yet it is undertheorized in relation to generative AI today (Benkler, 2006; Drott, 2021; Huang & Siddarth, 2023). The internet was once imagined as a knowledge commons, fostering decentralized collaboration and open access. Ranging from peer-to-peer sharing networks, to the free software movement and open source culture, to platforms like Wikipedia, and towards the darker sides of the internet like the Pirate Bay or the Darknet, the digital commons of the internet provide a diverse set of alternative models to those proposed by big tech. However, the shift to platform capitalism and data monetization, as described by Hunter (2002), led to the "anticommons" of the modern internet, where private control restricts access. Despite this, successful digital commons like Wikipedia and open-source software remain, demonstrating that cooperative structures can persist even within market-driven environments.

With the advent of large-scale AI the anticommons of platform capitalism underlines how openness and sharing—principles foundational to the digital commons of the internet—fuel both innovation and

exploitation (Peszowska, 2024). Openness and sharing enable a vibrant ecosystem of open-source software, public data, knowledge (like Wikipedia), and material infrastructures (such as Arduino) (Tarkowski, 2023). Yet, big tech's proprietary AI depends on accumulating data and resources from our natural and digital commons, profiting by reselling what was collectively ours as exclusive, value-added commodities (Bettig, 1997; Boyle, 2023; Jeffries, 2011; Tarkowski & Peszowska, 2024). At the same time, Silicon Valley releases systems in an "open" fashion, borrowing discourses from open source and free software movements (Widder et al., 2024). On closer inspection, released systems offer a varying degree of openness and transparency, as the LLM Openness Index indicates, muddling understandings of what "open" in fact means (Liesenfeld et al., 2023). In the best case, "open" AI systems allow for a degree of transparency and oversight. In most instances, powerful companies use the rhetoric and selective investment of "open" AI to strengthen market dominance, shape development standards, and benefit from unpaid open-source labor while resisting regulation (Widder et al., 2023). The key challenge posed to existing conceptual frameworks around the digital commons is described by Keller and Tarkowski (2021) as the "paradox of open," which presents "both a challenge to and an enabler of concentrations of power." A central question when it comes to envisioning a commons for AI in digital creation, then lies in critically investigating openness as well as exploring supplementary and alternative values.

AI Commons

The technology-focused legacy of creative commons, free software, and the open-source movement has informed the commons as a growing normative principle and governance framework in the AI community (Huang & Siddarth, 2023). The first of these efforts was the 2016 global AI Commons, an industry-driven organization that defines its mission as uniting leading experts to build an accessible AI knowledge hub that informs governance and supports inclusive, sustainable AI development, while also positioning itself on its website as a flexible platform for connecting problem owners and solvers. This definition underlines the ambiguity of the project and how interchangeable terms like hub, platforms, and commons can be in practice. A similar project, the MLCommons, was launched by corporate stakeholders in 2020 to establish common-pool resources to accelerate AI development. These efforts build on the commercialization of the open source and free software movement, albeit through extending these principles of common resource management to apply to the particularities of AI development, which includes model data and benchmarking tools (MLCommons, n.d.).

In contrast to these projects, which seek to continue the commercialization of digital commons into value-added commodities, an alternative ecosystem of commons and commons-adjacent projects in the realm of AI is emerging. First, the Creative Commons moved towards articulating its position on generative AI. These efforts began with a 2023 Global Summit where members of the global movement outlined seven principles for “regulating generative AI models in order to protect the interests of creators, people building on the commons (including through AI), and society’s interests in the sustainability of the commons” (Creative Commons, 2023).

Markedly focused on the labour issues discussed above, these principles led to a new online consultation known as an Alignment Assembly. An assembly’s constituent parts are worth spelling out as a way to note changes in the social movement. The Alignment Assembly is a collaboration between Creative Commons, Colombia’s Fundación Karisma, and the Open Future advocacy group, focused on sustaining the Internet as a “digital commons” with roots in the European Creative Commons movement (Hong, 2024). The term Alignment Assembly comes from the nonprofit organization Collective Intelligence Project, which emerged from the digital democracy movement. The Collective Intelligence Project has invested in seeking new forms of governance for AI, including the assembly process, which aims to develop alignment goals to guide generative and emergent AI systems.

Beyond the commercial and digital democracy streams, the commons as an approach to the development and governance of AI is proposed by a variety of diverse actors with diverse interpretations. Emerging from the open source community the Linux Foundation launched the Generative AI Commons project to develop an open source ecosystem for generative AI and its adoption on an organizational level (LF AI & Data, 2023). Moore (2025) provides insights on the impact of generative AI across the research cycle in the scholarly knowledge commons.

The scale of such AI commons is a central question. Varon et al. (2024) express the need for fostering a federated AI commons: an ecosystem for a diverse set of smaller organizations in opposition to big tech’s centralized, large-scale approaches to AI. On the other end of the scale, the Global Coalition for Tech Justice, an international network of more than 250 organizations, proposes the commons as a practical solution to implement the United Nations’ High-level Advisory Body on AI’s key principles and recommendations for global AI governance (Global Coalition for Tech Justice, 2025). Lastly, Public AI—i.e., the development of digital commons infrastructures in service of the public good—has been proposed as an alternative to the privatized approaches of big tech in Europe and North America. The

Public AI network, a consortium of organizations such as Mozilla, Open Future, and the Internet Archive, are spearheading discussions around this approach, including its relevance for the arts and the creative sector.

As these cases show, approaches to the AI commons are as multitudinous as the number of organizations devoted to the idea. Based on a review of 234 organizations including cooperatives, collectives, networks, companies, projects, and others across Africa, the Americas, and Europe, the organizations One Project and Coding Rights observe an emerging AI commons ecosystem that provides a diversity of alternative visions for the development and governance of AI (Varon et al., 2024). In other words, the power of the commons as a way of organizing lies in the ability to hold space for a wide range of approaches and perspectives.

Artistic, Creative, and Cultural AI Countergovernance

Artists and creators tend to find themselves at the tailend of exploitation, appropriation, and the repackaging of a cultural commons as value-added commodity to replace their creative labour by multimodal generative AI (Attard-Frost, 2023). The role of artists and creatives in the development and governance of AI largely functions along three thematic axes: copyright, creative labour, and artistic practices.

In terms of copyright, generative AI built upon the scraping and outright theft of artistic and creative works raises fundamental questions about the insufficiency of existing regimes of copyright protection and fair use. Fair use refers to limits on copyright for certain uses with clear public benefits, such as academic research, journalism, or artistic works (see Aufderheide & Jaszi, 2018). If copyright refers to the hegemonic approach to treating information as an intellectual property, even if palpably different from other kinds of property, then fair use concerns its exemptions—or the possibilities of commons amidst enclosures (Bannerman, 2016; Drahos & Braithwaite, 2002). On the other end of the spectrum, concerns arise among technological developers, lawyers, and policymakers if AI-generated works become copyrightable (Watiktinnakorn et al., 2023).

In terms of labour, the 2023 Hollywood strike initiated by the Writers Guild of America presents the most notable worker-led approach to AI governance, one that disrupted production in the sector and represented a powerful intervention in collective bargaining in the advent of AI (Grohmann et al.,

2025). Grohmann et al. (2025) highlight how the writers' strike illustrates worker-led AI governance through the convergence of three forms of power: institutional power rooted in a history of bargaining and resistance to technological change, economic power that secured unprecedented gains on both AI and long-standing demands like streaming residuals, and societal or discursive power amplified by widespread media visibility. Taken together, these dimensions make the Hollywood case a paradigmatic example of how workers can shape AI governance through historically and structurally grounded collective action.

Lastly, the innovative work of digital artists and cultural organizations explores concrete alternatives to dominant paradigms of AI. The Paris-based collective Dreaming Beyond AI serves as a platform for critical and generative inquiry, bringing together visionary fiction, speculative art, and community organizing to imagine more just and plural futures with technology. Festivals working at the intersection of art, music and technology, such as Barcelona's Sónar, Berlin's transmediale/CTM Festival, and Montréal's MUTEK, provide community-engaged spaces for the creative and discursive exploration of alternative AI practices and futures. Artists, such as Holly Herndon and Mat Dryhurst, not only critically investigate questions surrounding AI through their work but are invested in the practical development of technological alternatives. These include tools, such as Holly+, a tool that lets anyone upload a polyphonic track, which is then performed by an ethically sourced AI-generated deepfake of Holly Herndon's voice. Similarly, Public Diffusion presents an open source generative image model trained on ethically sourced training data (see Case Study 1). In particular, the Québec and Canadian art and technology context is home to critical artist-researchers, such as Sofian Audry (2021), whose book *Art in the Age of Machine Learning* highlights the critical role artists can play in pioneering new understandings and practices surrounding AI.

While these approaches underline key concerns and points of intervention within the existing regimes of copyright law and creative labour, as well as the innovative work of artists and cultural organizations in proposing alternatives, the collective investigation of how artistic, creative, and cultural ecosystems may need to transform remains underexplored. This then presents the starting point for our investigation of a commons for AI in digital creation in Québec and Canada.

Case Studies

Public Diffusion

Created in 2022 by a group of artists and musicians, Public Diffusion is a creative initiative in the field of generative AI and is notable for its commitment to ethical, commons-oriented development. The project's model is trained exclusively on images sourced from the public domain and those carrying Creative Commons "no rights reserved" (CC0) licenses. By avoiding the use of proprietary or copyrighted materials, Public Diffusion achieves a rare clarity in both legal and ethical terms: outputs generated through this model are unencumbered by third-party intellectual property rights. Public Diffusion operates as an open-source project with transparent documentation, accessible model weights, and an invitation to the community to participate in its ongoing development and governance. By rejecting extractive data practices, Public Diffusion addresses recurring concerns about big tech's appropriation of cultural labour and the exploitation of artist and creator communities. The initiative serves as a concrete example of how AI can support the broader goals of the digital commons, rather than undermine them. It offers an alternative to closed-source, profit-driven approaches to AI, prioritizing collective stewardship, mutual benefit, and the sustainable development of shared digital cultural resources. Public Diffusion's model not only catalyzes technological innovation but also aligns with growing calls for ethical, participatory infrastructures in the age of generative AI.

Future Art Ecosystems 4: Art x Public AI

Launched in 2024 by Serpentine Arts Technologies, *Future Art Ecosystems 4: Art x Public AI* (FAE4) is a landmark initiative hosting conferences and generating publications that advance a cultural vision for artificial intelligence as a public good. Developed through deep collaboration with artists, researchers, technologists, legal scholars, and policy actors, the project explores how AI can be controlled by and for the cultural sector, rather than imposed upon it. FAE4 distinguishes itself by embracing an ecosystemic approach to technological development: it promotes ethical data practices, shared infrastructures, and collective governance frameworks. Rather than exploiting proprietary models or data, FAE4 advocates for inclusive and sustainable systems that prioritize

transparency, artist agency, and cultural accountability. At its core, the initiative supports AI as a medium for artistic experimentation. From installations to simulations, FAE4 highlights how artists are reimagining the role of intelligence—natural or artificial—within immersive, participatory, and critical practices. It encourages the development of infrastructures that support these efforts, not just at the level of tools, but through institutional, legal, and civic collaboration. Operating at the intersection of ethics, public infrastructures, and creative technology, FAE4 sets out a roadmap for a more just and imaginative integration of AI into society. It offers an alternative to extractive, closed-source approaches to AI, proposing instead a vision rooted in the values of the digital commons: mutual benefit, collective intelligence, and the co-creation of shared cultural futures. Through its vision and actionable recommendations, *Future Art Ecosystems 4* stands as a vital reference point for shaping AI that serves the public artistically, ethically, and systemically.

Commons, Cooperativism, and AI in Québec and Canada

Québec and Canada present an ideal place to explore questions of the commons in relation to digital creation due to their long-standing history of commons and cooperatives, rooted in 18th- and 19th-century mutual aid societies, rural work-sharing, and Indigenous resource-sharing traditions. The Canadian Encyclopedia (Macpherson, 2015) highlights a cooperative legacy evolving through milestones such as Alphonse Desjardins's founding of the first *caisse populaire* in Lévis in 1900, farmer and worker cooperatives in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, and the rise of housing co-ops in the 1960s–70s. Modern examples include the Inuit cooperatives of Nunavik,⁵ which sustain cultural values while providing essential services, and sectoral federations like the Québec Council for Cooperation and Mutuality (CQCM), which foster governance, education, and advocacy.⁶ Nationally, movements like Antigonish spurred cooperative banking, retail, fishing, and housing initiatives, while the 1998 Canada Cooperatives Act strengthened democratic governance across sectors (Macpherson, 2015). Today, Québec and Canada's cooperative ecosystem encompasses thousands of co-ops across agriculture, finance, housing, retail, health, energy, and culture—representing millions of members, tens of billions in assets, and a deeply embedded culture of solidarity, self-governance, and collective enterprise.

⁵ For more information see the network of Nunavik co-ops, FCNQ-Ilagiisaq: <https://fcnq.ca/en/>

⁶ See <https://cqcm.coop/>

Cultural Commons in Québec and Canada

The concept of the cultural commons in Canada is rooted in the country's pluralistic foundations—Indigenous knowledge systems, settler colonial histories, and waves of immigration—shaped by practices of reciprocity, collective stewardship, and resistance to cultural enclosure. Indigenous oral traditions, ecological knowledge, and ceremonial practices form a long-standing commons, disrupted but not erased by colonial policies such as residential schools, and revitalized through contemporary cultural resurgence. Over the 20th century, state-led initiatives like the Canada Council for the Arts and CBC/Radio-Canada sought to build a shared national culture, often privileging dominant forms, while grassroots movements—from artist-run centres to community radio—expanded more decentralized, participatory modes of creation (Burgess & De Rosa, 2011; Dick et al., 2020).

In Québec, cultural commons have been shaped by the province's francophone identity, history of Catholic and later secular collectivism, and aspirations for cultural sovereignty. The *Révolution tranquille* of the 1960s played a transformative role in establishing robust state-led cultural infrastructures through public investments in institutions such as Télé-Québec and the Conseil des arts et des lettres du Québec alongside grassroots initiatives rooted in cooperativism and mutual aid (Conseil des arts et des lettres du Québec, n.d.; Gattinger & Saint-Pierre, 2011; Harvey, 2011; Télé-Québec, n.d.). Community radio, artist collectives, and neighborhood theatres fostered decentralized governance, linguistic and cultural protection, and broad access to cultural creation. Artist-run centres and cooperatives continue to provide spaces for experimentation, collective authorship, and inclusion, increasingly framed not only as artistic practices but as political and economic strategies for resisting market enclosure and fostering sustainability.

As highlighted in the commons literature, cultural commons in Québec are “not merely resources but practices of co-governance” that recognize both material and symbolic assets—spaces, tools, language, rituals, and shared imaginaries—as vital to collective flourishing (Bollier et al., 2015; Dardot & Laval, 2014; Furukawa Marques & Durand Folco, 2023). While global platforms threaten the visibility and viability of local creators, they also enable digital commons, such as open archives, localized Creative Commons licensing (e.g., via Communautique), and transmedia storytelling. Contemporary initiatives—from Indigenous cultural revitalization projects to Montréal-based media co-ops—foreground accessibility, reciprocity, and plurality, often calling for new forms of governance

that go beyond traditional state or market mechanisms by embracing hybrid models that combine public policy, cooperative structures, and grassroots innovation (Lévesque, 2008; Sengupta, 2015; Simpson, 2017; Tello-Rozas et al., 2025). As such, Québec’s cultural commons are part of a broader reimagining of the public sphere, emphasizing the importance of shared cultural resources as foundations for both identity and social cohesion.

AI and Tech Cooperativism in Canada

Québec and Canada have been central to both the technological development and governance of AI, with most activity concentrated in major hubs like Montréal and Toronto (McKelvey et al., 2024). While these hubs emerged in the mid-2010s, their foundations were laid in the 1980s and 1990s when Geoffrey Hinton and Yoshua Bengio—later joined by Yann LeCun—began their pioneering deep learning research (Senneville-Robert, 2021), which was supported early on by the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research (CIFAR). Hinton’s 2012 ImageNet win brought global attention to the connectionist approach, and the three shared the 2018 Turing Award for their work on deep learning. Bengio went on to found the Montréal Institute for Learning Algorithms (Mila) and the firm Element AI in 2016, reinforcing Montréal’s global standing. In 2017, Canada became the first country to adopt a national AI strategy, CIFAR’s Pan-Canadian AI Strategy (Hunt & Lepage-Richer, 2024; Radu, 2021), emphasizing research, talent attraction, ethical leadership, and multistakeholder policymaking (Kung et al., 2024). However, the 2022 tabling of the Artificial Intelligence and Data Act (AIDA) in the House of Commons caught many by surprise and was mired in controversy over its limited public consultation, vague scope, and absence of independent oversight, leading to its failure in Parliament (Attard-Frost, 2025; McKelvey et al., 2024). Despite frequent references to notions of ethical and responsible AI, Canada’s approach to the technical development and regulatory governance of AI is ultimately an industrial strategy focusing on economic growth and innovation with the provinces following a similar path (McKelvey et al., 2024).

The rise of tech cooperatives in Canada reflects an antithesis to the industrial approach to AI presented above. Tech cooperatives represent a growing movement to create ethical, democratic, and community-owned alternatives to the dominant tech industry, adapting traditional cooperative principles—democratic governance, mutual aid, and equitable access—to digital infrastructures, software development, and online platforms. While Canada has a long cooperative history in agriculture and finance, applying this model to technology is recent, emerging in response to gig

economy exploitation, tech industry inequality, and big tech monopolies (Lechat & Jay, 2023). According to Yu and Rizvi's (2025) *The 2024 Top Co-op Issues Survey Report*, there are 30–40 Canadian tech co-ops engaged in areas such as web and app development, cybersecurity, data hosting, IT training, and open-source tools for nonprofit and public interest groups, with examples including Hypha Worker Co-operative, Autonomic Co-operative, and Code Operative. These organizations often collaborate with social movements, environmental initiatives, and the arts, embedding solidarity and shared values into digital tools. However, challenges include limited awareness of co-op models in tech, financial pressures from serving underfunded clients, and outdated or ill-suited co-op legislation (Lechat & Jay, 2023). Despite this, tech co-ops are building distributed networks of mutual support, knowledge exchange, and policy advocacy, aiming to shift the political economy of technology towards transparency, justice, and collective ownership (Lechat & Jay, 2023).

Québec's long-standing cooperative tradition, emphasis on mutual aid (*entraide*), and robust provincial support structures have fostered a fertile environment for tech cooperatives, which exist alongside more than 3,000 co-ops in sectors like agriculture, finance (e.g., Desjardins), housing, and media (La Coopérative de développement régional du Québec (CDRQ), 2023b). Many tech co-ops—such as Communautique, Percolab Coop, Catalyse Coop, and Interface3—are deeply embedded in the province's social economy, operating at the intersection of digital innovation, participatory governance, and cultural production, often incorporating feminist, ecological, or decolonial perspectives. As noted in the *The 2024 Top Co-op Issues Survey Report* (Yu & Rizvi, 2025), Québec's legal and cultural frameworks offer tailored incorporation models, cooperative development funding, and educational programs (e.g., CDRQ), while initiatives like Coopérathon and Économie Sociale Québec promote tech aligned with commons-oriented, equitable, and public-interest values (La Coopérative de développement régional du Québec (CDRQ), 2023a). Despite advantages, co-ops face challenges such as competition from private firms, limited awareness of cooperative models, and difficulties implementing collective governance in fast-paced, hybrid work contexts (CoSocial). Nonetheless, strong transdisciplinary tendencies mean Québec co-ops often integrate technical services with training, research, and public engagement, reflecting a provincial vision that combines innovation with solidarity and roots digital infrastructures in shared governance and cultural specificity (Yu & Rizvi, 2025).

3. A Methodology for Commoning

To initiate our collective research we mobilized methods of situational analysis as put forward by Clarke et al. (2018). Situational analysis is specifically attuned to identifying the actors, issues, and their relationships, which are coproduced within the digital creative landscape in Québec and Canada. At the heart of situational analysis are various mapping exercises, which create visualizations of the actors and institutions as well as the issues they face in the situation, which we refer to as *A Potential Commons for AI in Digital Creation in Québec and Canada*. Situational analysis-inspired mapping begins with "messy" mapping and, through an iterative process of collective meaning-making, produces increasingly organized maps. As our research is community-centred, the majority of mapping exercises was accomplished collectively in a Miro board⁷ through a series of interviews with community members, online mapping workshops with stakeholders, and three in-person symposia in Montréal in November 2024, April 2025, and August 2025.

Figure 2: Consultation timeline.

May–Oct 2024 | Phase 1: Collective and Iterative Situational Mapping

During the first phase of the project from May to September 2024, we began convening a diverse constellation of actors from the field of digital creation in Québec and Canada— independent artists, scholars, cultural organizations, technologists, and research institutions—around three intersecting

⁷ For documentation of the situational mapping see https://miro.com/app/board/uXjvNZHvUUM=?share_link_id=507749421369

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

thematic work groups: (1) Social Sciences and Humanities, (2) Research-Creation, and (3) Technology. Initial participants were identified through the existing networks in digital creation of Sporobole and the Society for Arts and Technology and expanded via snowball sampling.

Between May and August 2024 we gathered participants for individual and group interviews. The findings of these interviews were distilled into written memos, which served as the basis for an internal workshop with working group leaders. The internal workshop translated memos and findings from interviews onto an evolving Miro board structured around the three original working groups, using colour-coded elements to distinguish organizations, people, technologies, documents, and thematic concerns. This visual map served not only as a knowledge repository but as an evolving cartographic tool for the iterative and collective mapping process.

Figure 3: Situational mapping.

From September to October 2024, the initial “messy map” evolved through a series of virtual mapping workshops with the three working groups using the Miro board. The iterative and collective process

allowed us to move from the initial working groups towards identifying key themes and issues, people and institutions, and tools and technologies of concern that cut across the digital creative ecosystem in Québec and Canada when it comes to the impact of AI. The mapping exercise generated new categories, such as accessibility, education, tools, data, governance, communities, infrastructures, publics, and industry relationships, which provided a more nuanced lens for understanding the field.

In early October 2024, this restructured map was presented back to the working groups during a series of feedback workshops, enabling participants to validate, contest, and expand upon the initial clusters. Rather than working from assumptions, this bottom-up process allowed for identifying what and who is already active in the ecosystem and their issues and concerns, as well as raising questions about who and what remains marginal, absent, silenced, or entirely excluded. Each thematic cluster was then articulated through concise visual and textual memos laying the groundwork for a transition from exploration to design. By late October, we had arrived at a more ordered and collectively constructed map of the current landscape, accompanied by a series of analytical memos that served as guiding materials for the November Symposium.

Nov 2024–Apr 2025 | Phase 2: In-person Consultations

The initial phase of interviewing, mapping, and thematic clustering laid the foundation for a first collective moment of synthesis. As the messy insights gradually took shape through internal and external workshops, what emerged was not only a more structured understanding of the ecosystem, but also a set of shared questions, concerns, aspirations, and tensions across communities. These elements converged into a series of thematic clusters—each pointing to areas ripe for exploration, intervention, or collaboration. With this groundwork in place, we convened three in-person symposia: a turning point designed to bring together the diverse voices consulted in the first six months of the project, not only to begin shaping concrete project ideas, but to create the conditions for new alliances, exchanges, and a collective reimagining of what a commons for AI in digital creation might become.

1st ArtIA Symposium

Dates: November 4–5, 2024

Location: Society for Arts and Technology (SAT), 1201 Boulevard Saint-Laurent, Montréal

Number of Participants: 41

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

The first ArtIA Symposium was a two-day event that brought together the artists, cultural workers, researchers, and technologists from the initial working groups and expanded the circle of participants to include other actors in the Québec and Canadian cultural ecosystem. The main objective of the symposium was to move from high-level discussions of the commons and those issues that emerged from the situational mapping to defining concrete measures and a preliminary plan of action for manifesting a potential Commons for AI in Digital Creation in Québec and Canada.

Figure 4: First ArtIA Symposium, November 4-5, 2024, at the Society for Arts and Technology. © Bruno Colpron.

The symposium was aimed at generating practice-based insights into developing both a conceptual understanding of a potential commons and material ideations. The symposium opened with presentations and a roundtable discussion on diverse understandings of the commons. The majority of the symposium was dedicated to collectively revisiting the thematic working groups identified through the previous situational mapping to enrich understandings and to brainstorm possible

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

solutions. Across six workshops participants explored questions of “Accessibility & Education,” “Artistic Practices,” “Communities & Publics,” “Data,” “Governance & Industry Relations,” and “Tools & Infrastructures.”

A key component of the symposium was centring artistic case studies by inviting artists, such as Marie-Ève Levasseur, Gadi Sassoon, Portrait XO, and Tegan Maharaj, to share concrete and hands-on examples of artistic questions and challenges in relation to AI, thus grounding at times abstract conversations around the commons in real-world experiences. The second day concluded with a project brainstorming session that presented an open and imaginative environment for participants to ideate desirable solutions to the many issues raised. The first ArtIA Symposium resulted in an enriched understanding of the issues at hand, in an expanded circle of participants and stakeholders, and a series of 20 concrete project proposals, which the participants deemed necessary to establish a commons for AI in digital creation in Québec and Canada.

After the symposium, the Society for Arts and Technology in collaboration with SYNTHÈSE hosted a networking cocktail. All independent artists and creatives, not affiliated with an academic institution, cultural organization, or private company were compensated for their participation (see Appendix X). The first ArtIA Symposium was documented in its entirety by project partners Projet Collectif with notes available on the Praxis platform.⁸

2nd ArtIA Symposium

Dates: March 31 and April 1, 2025

Location: Society for Arts and Technology (SAT), 1201 Boulevard Saint-Laurent, Montréal

Number of Participants: 37 + 205 Networking Cocktail

The second ArtIA Symposium was a two-day event that brought together the artists, cultural workers, researchers, and technologists from the initial working group and the first symposium, and it expanded the circle of participants again to include other actors in the Québec and Canadian cultural ecosystem. The main objectives of the second symposium were 1) to concretize discussions on previously identified project proposals, including the assessment of challenges, needs, and opportunities; 2) to expand on potential forms of governance for an AI commons in digital creation;

⁸ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/n/s4SzOELICQo2cg8xyV_iWCs8_Ys/

and 3) to present initial results to a broader audience including funders, government, and industry partners. Unlike the first symposium, which was invitation only, the second included an entirely public part in its programming.

*Figure 5: Second ArtIA Symposium, March 31 and April 1, 2025, at the Society for Arts and Technology.
© Bruno Colpron.*

The second ArtIA Symposium opened with a proposal and vision for a potential Commons for AI in Digital Creation shared by project partners Sporobole, Projet Collectif and the Society for Arts and Technology; it was followed by an open roundtable for participants to provide feedback and discuss. The afternoon of Day 1 was centred on exploring potential projects within the realms of “Model Crafting,” “Sustainable AI Tools,” “AI Imaginaries Incubation,” “Accessibility & Education,” “Common IT Infrastructures,” and “Small Data.” These sessions gave rise to three concrete projects, which were workshopped in-depth on the morning of Day 2. These were “Small Data and Model Crafting,” “Education & Training,” and “Shared Compute Infrastructures.”

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

The second half of Day 2 was dedicated to a public conference, which allowed the growing network of participants to share the collectively gained insights and pitch challenges, needs, and opportunities to an audience of artists, cultural organizations, academic institutions, funders, and government agencies. To ground conversations in the realities of artistic practice and material technologies, the second symposium again invited artistic case studies, including those from digital artist Marion Schneider, research-creator Gabriel Viglienson, Toronto-based UKAI Projects, the MUTEK AI Ecologies Lab, and the Wilding AI collective. The closing networking cocktail reception was accompanied by a series of technical demonstrations of creative AI tools by the Metacreation Lab at Simon Fraser University (Philippe Pasquier, Arshia Sobhan), Lab 148 (Emmanuel Durand, Michal Seta, Nicolas Bouillot), and the SAT innovation team (Manuel Bolduc, Charles Bicari, Jean-Michael Célérier).

Apr–Aug 2025 | Phase 3: Publication

After the second symposium the team worked on finalizing the publication of the results to be published as part of the third symposium, which took place on August 19, 2025.

3rd ArtIA Symposium

Date: August 19, 2025

Location: Society for Arts and Technology (SAT), 1201 Boulevard Saint-Laurent, Montréal

Number of Participants: 194

This last symposium concluded a year of stakeholder consultations. The main objectives of the third symposium were to publicly share the insights gathered in the past year; drive forward three concrete project proposals on small data and model crafting, training programs, and compute infrastructures; and launch the next chapter of the ArtIA consortium.

The ArtIA Symposium on August 19, 2025, featured a full-day program of talks and panels that presented the findings from *Towards a Commons for AI in Digital Creation* and explored how AI can be collectively governed to serve culture. Sessions included a keynote by Maurice Jones, Pía Baltazar, and Marek Blottière; a performance by dadabots; and a series of panels addressing themes such as hand-crafted AI and small data, AI literacy as a common good, collective strategies for funding and skills development, and the sovereignty of distributed infrastructures. The day concluded with the

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

panel “Weaving the links: AI for culture beyond borders,” situating ArtIA within broader international movements for artist-centred and collectively shaped AI systems.

Complementing the talks, the symposium also showcased a wide range of art and technology demonstrations, from AI music co-composition and gesture-driven performance tools to AI-powered visual systems, presented by partners including SAT’s Innovation Department, the Metacreation Lab, Laboratoire formes•ondes, Botto, and the Lab148. The evening culminated in FERAL FREQUENCIES, an immersive performance in the Satosphère developed by Wilding AI, which combined scenophony with AI-driven spatial audio. Together, the demos and performance illustrated how the ideas discussed during the day—commons-based infrastructures, new tools, and interdisciplinary collaboration—are already being put into practice within digital creative AI.

4. Prototyping an AI Commons

The iterative, collective, and participatory methodology outlined in the previous section resulted in generating new insights into what the current state of the digital creative ecosystem vis-à-vis AI is. More importantly, the process represented a concrete intervention into reshuffling networks, forming new and at times unlikely alliances grounded in common concerns, and it led to proposals for practical and material interventions to address identified challenges, needs, and opportunities. As such, the methodology not only generated thematic insights but also concrete prefigurations of possible commons and demonstrated our process as a form of commoning-in-action. The (re)configuration of working groups took place at three critical moments and directions:

- **Disciplinary Working Groups:** In April 2024, the initial configuration was framed by disciplinary boundaries, separating participants into three working groups—Social Sciences & Humanities, Technology, and Research–Creation—to investigate the question of a commons for AI in digital creation.
- **Interdisciplinary Thematic Clusters:** Leading up to the first ArtIA Symposium in November 2024, the iterative, collective process of situational mapping surfaced shared issues, needs, challenges, and opportunities that transcended the boundaries of the initial, disciplinary working groups. As such, the working groups reconfigured into a total of seven thematic working groups: Accessibility & Education, Artistic Practices, Data, Communities & Publics, Governance & Industry Relations, Tools & Infrastructures, and Sustainability.
- **Project Proposals:** The last reconfiguration of participants that took place between and during the first and second ArtIA Symposia generated new clusters along the lines of concrete project proposals to materialize a potential commons for AI in digital creation. During the first ArtIA Symposium participants brainstormed a list of 20 concrete project ideas ranging from educational programs, Fablabs, and glossaries to software tools and compute infrastructures. Based on interest and needs expressed by participants, the second ArtIA Symposium focused on developing three selected project ideas into concrete, actionable project proposals. The three developed project proposals are: 1) an open and accessible creative AI toolkit for digital artists, 2) an educational program for artists, creatives and cultural workers in digital creation, and 3) development of sovereign and accessible AI compute infrastructures for the digital arts in Québec and Canada.

Figure 6: Reconfiguration of working groups.

In the following paragraphs we trace the concrete and actionable insights generated in the three phases of working group configurations throughout the project. Tracing the process in-depth was made possible due to intensive note-taking by project leads and the support of project partner Projet Collectif, who collected insights from the the first and second ArtIA Symposia in a publicly available database.⁹

⁹ For information about Praxis, see <https://praxis.encommun.io/en/p/about-praxis/>. For documentation of the First ArtIA Symposium, November 2024, see <https://praxis.encommun.io/cn/-Hp2DdiBYkRwnJOY2HEpppofOHI/>. For documentation of the Second ArtIA Symposium, March/April 2025, see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/cn/8yZkLpNv54ygBnaQVh8t2SIUpTE/>.

Disciplinary Working Groups: On the Arts, For the Arts, In the Arts

Starting in April 2024 the initial approach of the project was centred around convening three disciplinary working groups related to the three different fields of activity. Following the three-fold model proposed by Annie Luciani (2011) these work groups focused on research on the arts via the Social Sciences & Humanities Working Group led by Ola Siebert, technological research and development for the arts via the Technology Working Group led by Philippe Pasquier, and research-creation in the arts via the Research-Creation Working Group led by Maurice Jones. Over the course of several weeks the working group leaders convened participants via a series of interviews and collective work sessions to establish a situational mapping of the current state of the creative AI ecosystem in Québec and Canada. The following section traces the work accomplished throughout these initial working groups.

Figure 7: Situational mapping of disciplinary working groups.

Social Sciences & Humanities

Lead: Ola Siebert

Participants: 10

The disciplinary working group on Social Sciences & Humanities (SSH) was initially tasked with fostering interdisciplinary dialogue among sectors, professionals, and artists engaged in AI projects, with a particular emphasis on integrating perspectives from the humanities and social sciences. By exploring the intersections of AI technology with technical and social practices, institutions, infrastructures, politics, arts, and culture, the group set out to

- map AI projects in production and track their social impact;
- maintain steady contact with partners to surface collaboration opportunities;

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

- survey the narratives, symbols, and speculative futures that frame AI across sectors; and
- articulate how SSH critiques could inform research–creation practices and technological R&D.

As work progressed, a core challenge emerged: the rapid tempo of an action-oriented commons project clashed with the slower cadence of critical SSH inquiry. Participants struggled to see how reflexive scholarship might join a timeline geared toward project prototyping and deployment. In response, the group reframed its mandate to focus on situated AI imaginaries as visions of possible creative AI futures voiced by artists in Québec and Canada, treating those imaginaries as a pragmatic bridge between critique and action. The group’s revised goals therefore became to

- identify and analyse artist-led imaginaries that shape perceptions of AI in Québec and Canada;
- translate those insights into concrete, culturally grounded recommendations in building an AI commons; and
- form a durable network of SSH actors ready to embed critical reflection within fast-moving ArtIA sub-projects.

Alongside this pivot, the group successfully mapped a constellation of SSH contributors (e.g., Lucas Larochelle, Rose Landry, Etienne Grenier, Nathalie Casemajor, Jonathan Roberge) and channelled them into emerging spin-offs: a “Futures Imaginaries” knowledge base, an ArtIA writing lab, and a public-facing podcast. Insights from this SSH exploration of AI imaginaries will directly inform Ola Siebert’s ongoing PhD dissertation at UQAM; Siebert is also a MITACS intern for this project.

Technology

Leads: Philippe Pasquier & Arshia Sobhan

Participants: 17

The Technology working group interviewed and convened 17 academics, art administrators, technologists, and practitioners to assess the current state of creative AI and to explore the possibility of developing an AI commons. The group focused on charting existing tools, surfacing challenges, and proposing recommendations for an inclusive, ethical, and adaptable infrastructures. The group’s initial objectives were to

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

- identify and document various AI tools, platforms, software, and libraries currently available across industry, academia, and community-driven initiatives;
- build an ontology/typology and provide a critical survey of the state of the art;
- identify needs and gaps in existing tools and infrastructures; and
- provide recommendations regarding the scope, design, and specifications of a future creative AI commons toolkit.

Throughout several weeks of interviews and collective workshops, shared values, key concerns, possible challenges, and tensions regarding a creative AI commons toolkit emerged. These included:

- **User accessibility and creative scope:** Develop tools that are intuitive and inclusive for both technical and nontechnical users while supporting a broad range of artistic disciplines and practices.
- **Open source vs. commercial solutions:** Evaluate how open-source software offers customization and community support compared to proprietary options that may be more user-friendly but less flexible.
- **Data sovereignty and small data:** Emphasize ethical data practices—including privacy, consent, and ownership—while supporting tools that perform well with limited datasets and enable context-specific, customizable use.
- **Online vs. offline; real-time vs. cloud:** Consider where AI tools run—locally, in the cloud, or in hybrid setups—while balancing real-time interactivity with available processing power.

Many of the conversations that followed, concerning the needs, usability, and accessibility of creative AI tools, were spearheaded by the Technology working group.

Research-Creation

Lead: Maurice Jones

Participants: 14

The disciplinary working group on Research-Creation was tasked with identifying the relevance of theoretically and practically developing a commons for arts-based and cultural AI. Born in Canada, Research-Creation (RC) is an interdisciplinary approach that employs creative art and design practices in fostering research across academia and the cultural sector. As such, the working group

gathered both academic and independent artist-researchers working in digital creation in Québec and Canada. The initial objective of the group was to explore the impacts of AI on critical research-creation practices, in particular surrounding questions of how AI may pose critical questions towards

1. theoretically and methodologically advancing research-creation practices;
2. articulating and circulating digital RC practices and outcomes beyond academic circles; and
3. training the next generation of RC practitioners.

The working group began with a series of individual virtual interviews, followed by group workshops conducted with participants from existing networks and expanded through a snowball method. The questionnaire invited broad reflections on the value and challenges of arts-based research, the role of AI in creative practices, and the potential of commons-based approaches.

Interviewees noted that research-creation practitioners faced persistent challenges in accessing infrastructures, navigating ethical concerns around digital technologies, and developing technological literacy. They emphasized the importance of beginning with conceptual inquiry rather than tools, preserving artistic autonomy, and engaging more critically with interdisciplinarity. In terms of AI, artists expressed a desire for more experimental and embodied interactions, beyond commercial platforms and prompt engineering, while calling for clearer definitions, educational support, and policy frameworks to ensure creative control and to avoid homogenization. Regarding commons-based approaches, interviewees highlighted the need for shared, inclusive infrastructures that offer diverse archives and equitable access, stressing the importance of data sovereignty, cultural specificity, and collaborative, community-driven policies.

Interdisciplinary Thematic Clusters

Following several weeks of interviews and collective work sessions the evolving situational mapping highlighted shared challenges and concerns that transcended the initial disciplinary working groups. Through the iterative mapping process, a set of thematic clusters emerged that required a reshuffling of initial disciplinary working groups towards interdisciplinary, thematic clusters, which presented the basis and subject of the first ArtIA Symposium in November 2024. The consolidated thematic clusters are:

- 1. Accessibility & Education**
- 2. Artistic Practices**

3. Data
4. Communities & Publics
5. Governance & Industry Relations
6. Tools & Infrastructures
7. Sustainability

The following section traces the advances of each interdisciplinary thematic working group achieved throughout collective work sessions and the two in-person Symposia in November 2024 and April 2025. In-depth insights are possible due to the extensive documentation work by ArtIA partner Projet Collectif. Documentation of the November and April Symposia is available on the open source Praxis note-taking platform.¹⁰

Figure 8: Thematic situational mapping.

¹⁰ For information about Praxis, see <https://praxis.encommun.io/en/p/about-praxis/>. For documentation of the First ArtIA Symposium, November 2024, see <https://praxis.encommun.io/cn/-Hp2DdiBYkRwnJOY2HEpppofOHI/>. For documentation of the Second ArtIA Symposium, March/April 2025, see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/cn/8yZkLpNv54ygBnaQVh8t2SIUpTE/>

Accessibility & Education

Drawing from diverse fields across the social and human sciences alongside artist-researchers, the Accessibility & Education cluster investigates the AI commons through an interdisciplinary lens. Its members, ranging from academic scholars to creative technologists, analyze how narratives, imaginaries, and pedagogical projects shape (and are shaped by) accessibility, ethics, and responsible AI. Grounded in methodologies from sociology, anthropology and Indigenous knowledge systems, the group began by thinking of treating AI as a shared resource, stressing the urgency of forging a common language to bridge conversations among all thematic clusters and train future artists in creative AI practices.

Figure 9: Working Group: Accessibility & Education during the first ArtIA Symposium.

Over the course of the first two symposia, the group's remit expanded: members realized that describing AI as a commons was not enough; they needed to design concrete pedagogical frameworks that would let future artists *inhabit* that commons. This pivot from conceptual mapping to actionable education now underpins all subsequent reflections:

- **Re-imagining arts education with AI:** Flipped, creativity-first pedagogies in which AI becomes a catalyst for exploration, prototyping, and knowledge-sharing aimed at “hacking” AI and diverting it from its more commercial use.

- **Ensuring accessibility and inclusivity:** Hardware access, adaptable learning styles, and safe spaces for underrepresented communities, supported by intersectional antibias resources.
- **Fostering critical and ethical AI literacy:** Curricula that equip artists to interrogate IP conflicts, dominant narratives, and algorithmic power dynamics through clear legal guidelines and reflexive practice.
- **Building durable art–science bridges:** Shared vocabulary and mediating formats (storytelling, podcasts, public exhibitions) that translate research into tangible, engaging outcomes.
- **Towards pluralistic AI commons frameworks:** Structures that let each community define its own mode of AI engagement with human mediation linking technology to cultural identity.¹¹

Arts and cultural education has emerged as the strategic arena for shaping a culturally responsible AI commons. Across both symposia, four imperatives converged:

- **Creativity–centred pedagogy:** Position AI as a medium for experimentation not an end in itself.
- **Equitable access and pluralism:** Empower marginalized groups and respect diverse modes of engagement.
- **Critical–ethical literacy:** Embed reflexive approaches that let artists question and reshape AI’s sociotechnical narratives.
- **Sustainable infrastructures:** Support learning with low–tech options, ongoing mentorship, and a pilot summer school to test and refine best practices.¹²

Several *crosscutting needs* also surfaced: technical empowerment, critical literacy, inter–sector mentorship, and equitable access to infrastructures. Participants stressed the value of *hybrid recognition models*—combining open badges or microcredits with creative autonomy—to link artistic relevance and academic acknowledgement. The envisioned summer school presented a first step towards a long–term interdisciplinary learning space: a living laboratory where sectors co–learn and co–create, laying the groundwork for a more permanent program recognized by both academic institutions and cultural organizations.¹³

¹¹ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/O7OyBpiXWEa3ZCfb8nFo1_whWWQ/

¹² For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/SEnFAakwd7n_sgariAWL53dl8k4/

¹³ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/CxUEXcOZ10JWib5vXLDHIHEV-k-w/>

Artistic Practices

Figure 10: Working Group: Artistic Practices during the first ArtIA Symposium.

While technology offers impressive advances in artistic mediums, AI introduces new challenges. This thematic cluster of the symposium explored AI's impact on artistic practices, highlighting key issues and aspirations. The interviews and workshops leading up to the symposium highlighted concerns around the homogenization of creativity, the need for culturally diverse and embodied approaches to AI, and the tension between artistic autonomy and powerful commercial tools. As the project is centred around developing an AI commons in digital creation, artistic and creative practices were foregrounded throughout both symposia—addressed through thematic work sessions, artistic provocations, and case study discussions that positioned artists' concerns as central to shaping an ethical, open, and inclusive AI commons.

The two thematic work sessions on artistic practices highlighted the following themes:

- **From individual to relational tools:** Participants critiqued the individualistic design of AI tools, proposing instead multi-user, multi-agent systems that support relational, collective creativity and unlock new forms of artistic collaboration.

- **Balancing artistic freedom with ethical responsibility:** Concerns about “art washing” and ethical blind spots prompted calls from artists and developers to foreground ethics, challenge algorithmic biases, rethink content discovery, and foster transparency in all stages of AI engagement.
- **Sustainability through preservation and adaptability:** To address tool obsolescence and tech churn, participants advocated for preserving artistic workflows through strategies like time capsules, interdisciplinary collaboration, and fluid, adaptable systems that maintain creative integrity.
- **Artists as advocates and visionaries:** Artists were seen as key agents of change with the power to critique and reimagine AI’s societal impact, suggesting they embrace collective action, critical experimentation, and visionary approaches to foster equity in AI development.
- **Redefining inclusion in AI practices:** The sessions called for a shift from tokenistic representation towards empowering marginalized communities to shape their own engagement with AI, emphasizing accessibility, data privacy, and ethical participation as foundational principles.¹⁴

These concerns were underlined by a series of concrete artistic case studies, in which digital artists shared their particular approaches to and challenges working with AI to highlight issues and needs that a potential commons for AI in digital creation may address:

- **Artistic curation in the age of AI overproduction:** Interdisciplinary artist **Marie-Ève Levasseur** emphasized the artist’s role as curator, carefully selecting from overwhelming AI-generated content to resist aesthetic uniformity and digital excess.¹⁵
- **Interdisciplinary, collective AI art practices: Gadi Sassoon, Portrait XO, and Tegan Maharaj** highlighted how their work on data sonification fostered interdisciplinary collaboration reflecting commons-based approaches to reclaim creative agency, demystify AI, and foster emotional engagement with complex data.¹⁶
- **Commons-based infrastructures:** Digital artist **Marion Schneider** advocated for collective infrastructures—like shared GPU access but also artistic spaces and residencies—to enable ethical, collaborative AI art practices.¹⁷

¹⁴ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/otAiCRz13RGcmmzjXZzZzP-oows/>

For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/qpHPCG-w7SH7bLSagey-GPZNij8/>

¹⁵ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/s4SzOELICQo2cq8xyV_iWCs8_Ys/

¹⁶ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/w6C69yexXHH5uY4kiPhsCZZagO4/>

¹⁷ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/NtOGq74QOoU-mOMIS6cJyaFIA/>

- **Art as cultural R&D:** Toronto-based collective **UKAI Projects** framed artistic practice as a mode of cultural research that challenges dominant technological paradigms—using language as a key example of how art can explore AI’s impact on perception, ambiguity, and collective meaning-making.¹⁸

Together, these reflections affirmed that artistic practice is not only a site of experimentation but a critical force in shaping the ethical, infrastructural, and cultural dimensions of an AI commons grounded in collective values and creative autonomy.

Data

The critical role of data in shaping the landscape of generative AI within artistic practices emerged as a key concern early across all three disciplinary working groups—Social Sciences & Humanities, Technology, and Research–Creation—and continued to shape discussions and reflections throughout the entirety of the project. Following the move from disciplinary to thematic working groups, Data represented a key theme explored across the November and April symposia.

Figure 11: Working Group: Data during the first ArtIA Symposium.

¹⁸ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/5rqj_JsyOZKwo3EYbldiYWI6SOE/

Two sessions during the November symposium focused on data-related questions in the context of AI and the arts. The first session raised several key concerns:

- **Data governance:** Artists need control over their data, including sovereignty and community-defined access protocols.
- **Diversity, inclusion, and accessibility:** Datasets must reflect underrepresented art forms and geographic diversity and be openly accessible with sustainable archiving.
- **Data quality and ethics:** Concerns included lack of accuracy, insufficient documentation, cultural insensitivity, privacy risks, and limited transparency.
- **Collaborative ecosystem:** A need for interdisciplinary partnerships, open-source tools, equitable funding, and targeted education to support artists' engagement with AI.¹⁹

The second work session continued where the first left off, raising concerns about the dominance of big data, unethical collection practices, and the lack of diverse representation while shifting toward concrete, artist-centred solutions. Key proposals included:

- **Small data and corpus management:** Support for tools that enable artists to work with curated, context-specific datasets suited to their creative needs.
- **Ethical and community-inclusive data collection:** Involving artists and communities in data governance to ensure respectful, accurate, and culturally sensitive practices.
- **Responsible data representation:** Providing technical resources and fair compensation to artists engaged in data processing, to maintain cultural and artistic integrity.²⁰

The second symposium advanced the concretization of an artist-centred AI toolbox through two dedicated work sessions. Rooted in core values of **accessibility, inclusion, ethics, sustainability, autonomy, open source, modularity, interoperability**, and **respect for creators and data**, participants collectively envisioned a lightweight, customizable, and ethical tool box that is:

- **Technically adaptable**, supporting multiple data types (audio, video, text, 3D), robust data management and long-term archiving, modular design, and hardware-agnostic interoperability (e.g., compatibility with Hugging Face, Arduino, ONNX).
- **Artist-friendly**, requiring minimal programming knowledge and supporting use on affordable hardware.

¹⁹ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/G-UBzsQtzMfjMtO9DcLIHL_42Fk/

²⁰ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/gzOMCaJydgmNLGydVkXtCi8GDxs/>

- **Community-grounded**, enabling autonomy in creative generation, interpretation, and the archiving of artworks as well as documentation and knowledge sharing through a learning community.²¹

The sessions also emphasized a strong **pedagogical and community-centred approach**, calling for:

- **a multilayered interface** adaptable to various skill levels (inspired by tools like Tinkercad and Arduino);
- **conversational mediation tools** to simplify access to complex concepts without losing technical precision; and
- **a shared governance model** to support collaborative decision-making, prevent power imbalances, and ensure the tool's long-term sustainability.²²

Key challenges identified included the risk of overgeneralization, difficulties in stable implementation, governance-related tensions, and securing long-term funding. As a solution, participants proposed leveraging existing open-source tools and building a **shared infrastructures** to manage and host corpora, disseminate creative work, and foster cross-disciplinary experimentation—centring artists' values while reducing reliance on big tech.

Communities & Publics

While ArtIA began as a symposium, it quickly evolved into something more: a community. From its earliest edition, it created a space where artists, researchers, and technologists could explore how collaborative artistic practices in AI intersect with broader social and cultural dynamics.

Two sessions during the first symposium focused specifically on the role of communities and publics in shaping the future of creative AI. The first session highlighted the needs for

- **Community-aligned development:** Strengthen existing artistic communities by co-creating AI tools that reflect their values, support governance, and address their specific needs.
- **Building bridges between communities:** The potential of an AI commons as connective infrastructures to foster dialogue and collaboration both among diverse communities and between communities and the broader public.

²¹ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/u_DY6CB4cJH7gWtIDXp5SlipoRo/

²² For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/S271udxLHzZb1p7m4MRiqdSciks/>

- **Empowering community-centred organizations:** Support and empower existing organizations like libraries to act as digital commons that enhance access, foster discoverability, and facilitate artist-controlled data trusts for data sovereignty and creative autonomy.
- **Negotiating with industry:** Advance community-driven strategies like collective bargaining and alternative ownership models to empower artists and challenge tech monopolies.²³

Overall, participants noted that many meaningful alliances are grounded in real-life interaction, underscoring the value of physical space and presence in sustaining artistic ecosystems. Rather than positioning communities as passive users, the symposium framed them as active agents in co-creating the conditions, tools, and governance structures necessary for an equitable AI art ecosystem.

Figure 12: Mapping exercise of the Communities & Publics Working Group.

²³ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/jiFeLufM0kpa5hLkQpOKIxPBCK4/>

While the first session explored an ideal way for communities to engage with, in, and through an AI commons, the second session highlighted a series of concrete challenges and concerns that need to be addressed. These included:

- **Multidimensional nature of community building:** Building sustainable AI-art communities requires balancing social, technical, and logistical dimensions.
- **Equitable, community-centred access:** Artists need community-managed spaces for equitable access to AI tools and digital literacy.
- **Community data ownership and governance structures:** Ensuring artist control over data demands new governance models like data trusts and cooperatives.
- **Empowering bottom-up governance:** Community-led governance offers an alternative to corporate control, but requires legal and organizational support.²⁴

Together, these insights affirm that building a community-centred AI commons requires not only shared ideals but also sustained, grounded practices of collaboration, care, and collective agency.

Governance & Industry Relations

Figure 13: Working Group: Governance & Industry Relations during the first ArtIA Symposium.

²⁴ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommuni.io/b/artia/n/99-6aqwl.ZOW7ycgpyNuTKQgUIRg/>

A key concern across the working groups was how to structure governance within an AI commons—both internally among artists, researchers, and institutions and externally in relation to the private sector. Discussions raised questions about ethical governance models, engagement with industry without compromising values, and the potential for noncommercial, artist-led initiatives that maintain autonomy and foster responsible partnerships.

These questions framed the first symposium, which hosted two dedicated work sessions on governance and industry relations. In terms of governance questions the work sessions highlighted the need to:

- **Define the creative AI commons and its stewardship** through noncommercial, community-based governance models that ensure artists retain control over data and gain access to resources and knowledge inspired by established cases, such as public libraries and cooperative governance.
- **Establish artist-centric governance** to address power imbalances with industry by promoting fair representation, bottom-up structures, and collective negotiation.
- **Develop new legal and economic frameworks**, such as data trusts, UBI, and legal clinics to support fair compensation and intellectual property protection in AI-driven arts.²⁵

Drawing inspiration from models like Wikipedia, this artist- and community-centred governance may become a power base to protect artists' interests and navigate power imbalances with industry, particularly big tech corporations. Participants highlighted the need to:

- **Reimagine tech sector relations** by exploring models that redirect big tech profits to support the arts while maintaining creative autonomy and accountability.
- **Balance negotiation and autonomy** through structures like data trusts, cooperatives, and associations while debating whether engagement with industry or radical independence is the more ethical path.²⁶

In response to emerging concerns, ArtIA updated its vision and roadmap, presenting it at the second symposium through a presentation and roundtable discussion. The session reaffirmed commitments to open, community-driven digital commons and critical engagement with AI, while exploring

²⁵ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/rsj-QlOOH4w93nmOdF2O4QNLaXo/>

²⁶ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/boOfrxSh-Eb4DbOOi07mbWfNgRU/>

cooperative governance, shared ownership, and collective decision-making.²⁷ Giving feedback to the renewed vision, participants raised concerns regarding:

- **Funding:** While acknowledging that funding is currently flowing into AI, participants stressed the importance of strategically accessing these resources without losing sight of artistic values, autonomy, and critical engagement with the technology.
- **Capitalization and collective ownership:** Calls were made to ensure that tools developed within shared infrastructures become collective property, and that cross-sector collaboration is prioritized to strengthen both impact and funding potential.
- **Mutualization and resource sharing:** Sharing technologies and resources can improve access and reduce redundancy but raises coordination challenges—especially when partnering with institutions that may conflict with the community’s values. Clear strategies are needed to navigate these tensions.
- **Role and autonomy of artists:** Safeguarding the central role of artists within multistakeholder projects was emphasized, ensuring that artistic practice remains at the core while engaging other sectors meaningfully.²⁸

Taken together these sessions and discussions aided in developing a shared understanding of what a commons for AI in digital creation may look like in terms of the practicalities of facilitating multistakeholder relationships.

²⁷ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/ktUUL8NH0zdyiixW9qM6V7YqQyQ/>

²⁸ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/e6E5YID5MdEIWGE-GGQCdQi5GNI/>

Tools & Infrastructures

Figure 14: Mapping exercise of the Tools & Infrastructures working group.

As generative AI transforms creative practice, the technological infrastructures supporting these tools become increasingly critical to artistic production. The Tools & Infrastructures working group examined the technical foundations necessary for accessible and ethical AI art creation. The group focused on identifying key technological tensions, from the divide between open-source and commercial solutions to the balance between local and cloud processing. A central concern was democratizing access while maintaining the technical depth required for sophisticated artistic practice, emphasizing the need for solutions that serve both technical and nontechnical users. The group aimed to establish recommendations for an AI commons toolkit that addresses these challenges while promoting ethical considerations and artist empowerment.

The Tools & Infrastructures working group began by auditing the infrastructures powering creative AI systems: GPUs, storage, software frameworks, cloud/local compute stacks, models, and interfaces. The group treated tech infrastructures as a cultural commons that must stay moddable, transparent and resistant to censorship. Their overarching objective was to develop an “AI commons toolkit” that

enables both technically proficient users and nonspecialist creators to initiate, adapt, and repurpose AI pipelines independently, free from institutional gatekeeping or exploitative licensing models.

The group explored these initial discussion during the first ArtIA Symposium, highlighting the following concerns:

- **Access is not an afterthought:** Artists face steep hardware costs and steep learning curves. The group emphasized clear tutorials, low-tech on-ramps, and no-code interfaces (with direct manipulation where possible) to bridge the gap.
- **Ethics in the kernel:** Dataset transparency, data sovereignty, and anticensorship defaults were deemed nonnegotiable. Local compute and community-run platforms offer the strongest guarantees.
- **Small data and model crafting:** Empower artists to use their own data and craft custom models, taking control of the full production chain. Small data approaches also offer eco-friendly tactics to reduce AI art's carbon footprint.²⁹

The second symposium added further depth to questions surrounding technology and infrastructures including concerns around:

- **Tech sovereignty: not vendor lock-in** – A shared GPU pool (borrow-a-box + remote cluster) was pitched as the quickest pilot toward collective autonomy.
- **Centralized vs distributed** – Participants debated a single hub against a mesh of nodes; resilience and self-governance tipped the scales towards the latter.
- **Infrastructures = Hardware + People** – Governance models, access policies, and recognition protocols matter as much as silicon. The group identified needs for the entire production chain to become a commons.³⁰

Key recommendations emphasized creating and advocating for an infrastructural AI commons by treating GPUs, storage, and APIs as shared resources, supported through borrow-and-return hardware libraries, open-source model hubs, and remote clusters with fair-use quotas, following a roadmap from inventory and pilot clusters to a federated mesh and a fully documented, copyleft-licensed

²⁹ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/nNO7WOK5OJuD_ervZP4y_6djFzU/
For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/5gu_ruAkcRJdlEa00ycvuHSvSV8/

³⁰ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/id80E3sbdpf7pl6Pp84LMCbt6lY/>
For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/u_DY6CB4cJH7gWtIDXp5SljpoRo/

AI-commons toolkit. These infrastructures should embed ethical and ecological guardrails at every layer, including dataset transparency, carbon tracking, and anticensorship/antibias safeguards. The overarching vision was expressed for every creator—from command-line experts to nontechnical storytellers—to have root access to the AI commons without compromising ethics, sustainability, or creative freedom.

Sustainability

Sustainability emerged as a critical yet underrepresented question during the first ArtIA Symposium in November 2024. Inspired by these concerns and after revisiting the initial situational mapping, the second ArtIA Symposium in April 2025 included a work session focusing on the intersection of sustainability and AI. The workshop explored the notion of sustainable development in relation to AI tools and digital creation, aiming to identify key questions and the stakeholders involved in order to find solutions. Sustainability emerged as a complex concept, viewed from multiple perspectives, encompassing socioeconomic, ethical, and financial dimensions beyond just ecological concerns.

Figure 15: Mapping exercise of the Sustainability working group during the second ArtIA Symposium.

The discussions highlighted major issues such as the environmental impact of large-scale training and data centers as well as the technical instability of new AI tools. The working group highlighted:

- **Thinking long-term:** Integrate environmental, social, and technological impacts into the design of AI projects.
- **Decentralization and resource sharing:** Promote local, shared, and accessible infrastructures to strengthen community autonomy.
- **Solidarity and ethical respect:** Anchor projects in principles of social justice, transparency, and respect for all living beings.
- **Bridging knowledge and fostering collaborations:** Encourage unlikely alliances and highlight community-based expertise, notably diverse Indigenous knowledge systems.
- **Collective maintenance and long-term sustainability:** Organize the upkeep of systems and build living networks of skills and competencies to ensure their lasting evolution.³¹

Rather than an afterthought, these concerns should be addressed across the entirety of the AI development and deployment cycle in digital creation.

Project Proposals

The last reconfiguration of participants that took place between and during the first and second ArtIA Symposia generated new clusters along the lines of concrete project proposals to materialize a potential commons for AI in digital creation. During the first ArtIA Symposium participants brainstormed a list of **20 concrete project ideas**.

Among others, participants proposed an online platform, inspired by Shadertoy, that consolidates and shares open AI and artistic resources—such as databases, tutorials, pre-trained models, research, and projects—while fostering collective intelligence through archiving, interconnection with other libraries, and institutional partnerships. Diverse educational and training proposals included workshops, online tutorials, short programs, and mentorships pairing artists with technical assistants to democratize AI in the arts. These initiatives emphasize ethical, cultural, and inclusive approaches, integrating critical AI literacy, generative art modules, and accessible resources to support underrepresented groups and broaden public engagement. Public communication efforts like a dedicated writing group to develop the conceptual foundations of an AI commons, produce accessible academic and nonacademic

³¹ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/b/artia/n/ICGFyadw2HOZglwMXP-LDpYJx4Q/>

publications, and shape future communication strategies were suggested alongside a podcast serving as the project’s public face, highlighting initiatives, sharing research–creation practices, and fostering critical discussions on arts, AI, and imaginaries.

Based on these 20 project ideas, participants selected **three projects to develop into concrete, actionable proposals**. The three developed project proposals are 1) an open and accessible creative AI toolkit for digital artists, 2) an educational training program for artists, creatives, and cultural workers on AI in digital creation, and 3) developing sovereign and accessible AI compute infrastructures for the digital arts in Québec and Canada. These three projects are covered in chapter 6, *Building an AI Commons*.

Title	Theme	Description
Library Project	Accessibility & Education	Create an online platform (inspired by Shadertoy) bringing together databases, tutorials, feedback, pretrained AI models, research articles, and art projects. This library would enable sharing, archiving, pooling, and interconnection with other existing libraries. It is a tool for consolidating knowledge and inspiration, fostering collective intelligence.
Education and Common Knowledge Infrastructures	Accessibility & Education	Develop training courses, workshops, online tutorials, short programs, train-the-trainer courses, wikis, and self-help forums aimed at democratizing AI in the arts. The aim is to equip artists—and beyond, a broad audience—with the tools and skills they need to understand, create, and critique AI works and devices.
Technical Mentorship Programs for Artists and Creatives	Accessibility & Education	Linking artists with technical assistants to learn programming, explore the limits of AI, and develop inclusive tools. An intersectional approach and the creation of safe spaces are at the heart of the initiative.
AI in Education	Accessibility & Education	Rethinking education through the creative integration of AI in flipped classroom models and interdisciplinary approaches linking arts and sciences at the university level.
AI Lexicon	Accessibility & Education	Create a lexicon of AI-related terms suitable for artists new to the field, using accessible stories to demystify technical concepts.
Imaginaries of AI	Artistic Practices	Knowledge database on future and technological imaginaries expressed in the arts, narratives, and collective visions of the world shaped by culture and technology.
Writing Group	Artistic Practices	Laboratory for reflection on the AI commons based on artistic practices and field research. Aims to articulate, disseminate, and communicate an

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

		accessible and inclusive vision.
Creative AI Podcast	Artistic Practices	Create a podcast as a public showcase for the ArtIA project, bringing together stories, testimonials, artistic initiatives and critical discussions on the intersections between art and AI.
Communication Channels	Communities & Publics	Develop alternative communication channels that embody the values of commonality: transparency, decentralization, and cross-sector collaboration.
Data Archivist	Data	Create an easy-to-use corpus manager for artists, including data preprocessing and packaging tools for creating small-scale AI models.
Cooperative Governance Structures	Governance & Industry Relations	This project addresses the often-overlooked infrastructures of governance within the development of AI commons. It aims to explore how decision making, accountability, and collective ownership can be embedded structurally in tools, institutions, and artistic processes.
Common Compute Infrastructures (Short Term)	Tools & Infrastructures	This project addresses the lack of compute access for artists. It proposes to consult the community, develop a shared infrastructures with partners, and advocate for governmental support.
Common Compute Infrastructures (Long Term)	Tools & Infrastructures	Long-term plan to implement robust shared infrastructures for artists. May include archival or capsule-based solutions supporting open-source workflows.
Accessible Ethical Small Data and Model Crafting Tools	Tools & Infrastructures	This project develops artist-friendly tools for small data and modeling, prioritizing no-code, no-upload, open-source principles. It emphasizes ethical, local, and inclusive practices.
Distributed Computing	Tools & Infrastructures	Develop distributed computing architectures to support artistic creation. Promotes decentralized, resilient infrastructures aligned with commons logic.
Culturally Diverse Multi-Agent Systems	Tools & Infrastructures	Reimagine AI multi-agent systems to reflect cultural diversity. Design ecosystems of agents based on varied cultural logics and artistic approaches.
Time Capsules for Sustainable Workflows	Tools & Infrastructures	Create a time capsule for artistic workflows—archiving full toolchains, stacks, and conditions for reproducibility and sustainability.
AI Fablabs	Tools & Infrastructures	Establish a one-stop shop for AI and the arts. Inspired by maker culture, it combines physical and digital resources for learning, production, and collaboration.
Sustainable AI Tools	Tools & Infrastructures	This project explores sustainable, low-energy, and ethical AI tools for digital arts, aiming to reduce ecological and social impact.

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

Critical Communications Toolkit on Creative AI	Tools & Infrastructures	Prototype communication tools aligned with commons values: transparency, care, reflexivity. Designed for collaborative artistic and research contexts.
---	----------------------------	--

5. Intermezzo: Reimagining a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

Over the course of 18 months we consulted more than 200 participants in exploring what an AI commons in digital creation may be. While there were several conversations that explicitly addressed the commons conceptually, the majority of exchanges focused on concrete, practical, and material interventions rather than conceptual musings. Yet, while not specifically addressing the commons, these exchanges implicitly expressed concerns about possible futures that are marked by alternative models to working, living, and co-creating in the age of AI. Researcher and intern to the project Ola Siebert tracked these conversations over the course of the three symposia through an ethnographic lens, investigating the sociotechnical imaginaries expressed by participants. Sociotechnical imaginaries, as defined by Sheila Jasanoff (2015), reflect collective visions of how life should be lived through science and technology. AI creators, by envisioning future technologies in relation to society, help shape new imaginaries that are dynamic, situated, and deeply intertwined with identity, politics, and ethics.

When discussing sociotechnical imaginaries, we encounter multiple, often competing, narratives about AI and the futures we deem desirable. These narratives have long shaped our collective imagination, influencing how we understand the past, experience the present, and anticipate what lies ahead. From Homer's ancient tales of artificial servants (Thomas & Liveley, 2020) to today's advanced technologies—such as machine learning, image generators, ChatGPT, and robotic surgeons—myths, legends, and speculative stories have continuously informed our perceptions of AI and its potential evolution. Although often viewed as a phenomenon of the future, AI is inseparable from its past: a history embedded in storytelling, mythology, and speculative fiction that is constantly reimagined in the present. As Mager and Katzenbach (2021) remind us, the future is not simply imagined—it is actively constructed, deconstructed, and reconstructed through sociotechnical processes. These futures are also contested terrains, shaped by both public governance and the strategic narratives of multinational corporations that exploit “perceived hopes and fears” to influence consumers (Jasanoff, 2015, p. 27). These narratives play a crucial role in discussions around the AI commons, whose goal is to foster and develop desirable future technologies that hold meaning for AI creators. Envisioning possible futures helps define goals, sources of inspiration, and motivations for developing technologies that are not only useful and innovative but also ethical.

The first symposium framed the commons not as a fixed model, but as a living, evolving concept—one that adapts to the needs of specific communities and contexts. Discussions highlighted how AI both relies on and challenges the commons: it draws from shared resources such as open data, but also intensifies concerns around ownership, governance, and sustainability. Participants emphasized that resilient imaginaries for the AI commons must be rooted in diversity, decentralization, and inclusive governance—especially within the artistic and creative sectors. Examples such as Wikimedia illustrated how financial sustainability (e.g., monetizing APIs) can coexist with openness and accessibility. The conversation also drew on Indigenous and relational knowledge systems, offering alternative models of stewardship, community-based decision making, and ethical engagement. In this vision, artists and creators play a key role in resisting market-driven platform logics, imagining alternative infrastructures, and rethinking the commons as a dynamic, equitable space for collective innovation and cultural flourishing in the digital age.

Beyond shared resources, the commons demands innovative governance models that ensure both long-term sustainability and broad accessibility. One promising approach discussed was the monetization of infrastructures rather than content, offering a balanced path forward. The symposium also emphasized the power of collaboration rooted in mutual respect and collective problem-solving. Diversity—of expertise, background, and perspective—was highlighted as a catalyst for innovation, enabling more holistic responses to complex challenges. A key insight was the importance of linking local, grassroots initiatives to institutional and political structures. Building alliances with policymakers can amplify the systemic impact of commons-based projects. Finally, the need to move from reflection to action emerged clearly, with structured exercises like the Troika dialogue helping translate shared spaces into concrete outcomes. Ensuring sustainability was framed as a shared responsibility, requiring both technical solutions and systemic shifts in practice to address structural inequalities.

The imaginaries of AI creators were further developed during the AI Imaginaries Incubator, held as part of the second symposium. This working group focused on envisioning desirable futures and the kinds of technologies that might accompany AI creators in those futures. These questions were discussed as integral—not only to the development of artistic and technological projects, but also to the evolution of society itself. Imagining desirable futures requires recognizing the deep interconnections between technology, art, science, and politics. The Imaginaries Incubator emphasized curiosity and play as essential to reimagining AI—not as a fixed object, but as a set of tools with the potential to nourish new commons and support collective creativity. Participants emphasized that imaginaries are

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

not limited to AI as a technology, but rather to what AI enables: new tools, metaphors, and relational possibilities. Participants questioned whether AI could be reclaimed from extractive attention economies to support deeper systemic change. Ultimately, AI was reframed as a means rather than an end—a catalyst for rethinking humanity, governance, and shared futures through the lens of the commons.

6. Building a Commons

In the latest phase, the working groups reorganized around three concrete projects chosen from the original list of 20 proposals. These projects focus on the key pillars participants identified as essential for building an AI commons for digital creation in Québec and Canada: software tools, critical learning resources, and compute infrastructures. During the second symposium, participants refined their visions of what these projects should achieve. Between the second and third symposia, the groups continued developing the proposals and began translating elements of them into concrete actions. The third and final symposium served as a public forum for feedback, not only presenting findings and proposals but also engaging potential partners to help drive these projects forward.

Small Data and Model Crafting: Artisanal AI Tools, Methods, and Practices

This project aims to design and implement a modular, open-source, and artist-friendly AI toolkit that prioritizes small data, local computation, and ethical creative sovereignty. It responds to a widely recognized gap in the current AI tools landscape: the lack of accessible, secure, and sustainable systems aligned with the specific needs of artistic creators. Instead of scaling up into massive cloud-based platforms, we propose scaling down—developing lightweight, customizable, and community-oriented AI systems that foster creative autonomy and public good.

Community Consultations, Shared Concerns

Concerns about the current state of generative AI surfaced early in the ArtIA process, particularly during the first two symposia and the focused meetings of the Technology Working Group led by Philippe Pasquier. Artists, researchers, and technologists voiced shared frustrations with the dominance of opaque, corporate-led AI systems that rely on large-scale data harvesting, closed-source infrastructures, and cloud-based deployment. These models, while technically impressive, often undermine artistic needs by prioritizing profit, surveillance, and scalability over creative autonomy, ethical transparency, and sustainability. Participants highlighted the inaccessibility of coding-heavy tools, the ecological cost of cloud computing, and the exploitative use of data—often gathered without consent from artists and cultural practitioners.

In response to these concerns, a common set of desires began to emerge: the need for AI tools and infrastructures that are local, ethical, accessible, and artist-controlled. Throughout the consultation the particular specifications of such tools emerged as:

- **No Cloud:** Preference for local generation due to security, ecological, and practical concerns.
- **No Coding:** Need for accessible tools with GUI, real-time feedback, and layered interfaces.
- **No Big Data (without consent):** Tools should support user-defined training data and resist exploitative data practices.
- **Support for Model Crafting and Iteration:** Artists want to train, remix, and iterate on their own models.
- **Open Source:** Transparency and community trust through shared code.
- **Free or Publicly Accessible:** Aligning with pedagogical goals and principles of the AI Commons.³²

These specifications, consolidated through extensive community dialogue, were then investigated through an analysis of 122 existing AI tools by the Technology Working Group (see Appendix III). The results confirmed the gap—while many tools partially aligned with these emerging values, only eight fulfilled the full set of criteria. This clear mismatch between artistic needs and available technologies has driven the development of the Small Data and Model Crafting Toolkit, a project grounded in principles of openness, small data, local compute, and customizable systems. It aims to reclaim agency for artists and cultural workers by offering tools designed for creative sovereignty rather than corporate extraction.

Objectives

Together with the community the Small Data and Model Crafting project emerged to accomplish two concrete objectives:

1. Design and develop an AI toolkit that meets the specifications emerging from ArtIA's consultation process.
2. Study and document artistic research-creation practices that use such tools, developing new methodologies for small data-driven creative work.

³² For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/n/S271udxLHzZb1p7m4MRiqdSciks/>

Roadmap

The development of the project is underway, driven by the leadership of a committed team of researchers, artists, and organizations who bring both technical expertise and deep involvement in artistic communities. Two research subventions are currently sought:

- **Objective 1 (Tool Development)** is led by Philippe Pasquier (NSERC Alliance Society PI) in collaboration with Gabriel Vigliensoni with institutional support from ArtIA, MUTEK, Sporobole, VIVO, and SAT. The application is being written as this report is being compiled, to be submitted in Fall 2025. Unlike usual NSERC proposals, this project will be designed to both advance scientific knowledge while serving the community of stakeholders (this is the “Society” part of the project, which aims to positively impact the community from which the need emerged). To achieve this we will use participatory design that involves stakeholders (be they artists or artistic organizations).
- **Objective 2 (Research–Creation Study)** is led by Gabriel Vigliensoni (SSHRC Insight PI), with coapplicants Dominic Thibault, Philippe Pasquier, and Erin Gee with support from SAT (Edu Meneses), AKOUSMA, CIRMMT, and other cultural stakeholders. The application is being written as this report is being compiled, to be submitted Fall 2025.

Stakeholders and Governance

A self-selected mix of academics, community organizations, and practitioners lead these grant application projects:

- Philippe Pasquier (NSERC Alliance PI), Simon Fraser University
- Gabriel Vigliensoni (SSHRC Insight PI), Concordia University
- Dominic Thibault and Erin Gee, Université de Montréal
- Edu Meneses, SAT
- Representatives from ArtIA, MUTEK, Sporobole, VIVO (mostly for expression of support and outreach activities).

At this stage, the precise composition of the team—including the research group, highly qualified personnel, and research participants—remains to be determined. Equity, diversity, and inclusion considerations are central to this process. Particular attention will be given to ensuring that the range of stakeholders reflects diversity not only across roles—such as researchers, established artists, content creators, emerging practitioners, learners, and educators—but also across other relevant dimensions of representation.

ArtIA Summer School: A Knowledge Commons for Creative AI

In Québec, the growing intersection of art and AI is met with a fragmented and insufficient training landscape. While a few technical programs exist—such as the Attestation of College Studies certificate and other forms of continuing education funded by Emploi Québec and offered by private institutes—they remain scattered and difficult to access. Artists and creative professionals seeking to engage with AI encounter a decentralized and complex network of opportunities, with little to no centralized platform to guide them. Recent efforts to map the training ecosystem in Québec revealed nearly 3,000 programs, yet none offer a coherent, dedicated path for artists and cultural workers wishing to develop both technical fluency and critical insight around AI. Furthermore, no single platform currently aggregates this information, though one is in development by Pôle Synthèse. This dispersion, combined with bureaucratic and structural challenges, limits the ability of artists to engage meaningfully with technological innovation and hampers the growth of an inclusive, creative AI ecosystem in the province.

Community Consultations, Shared Concerns

This is the context in which the idea of an *Art & AI Summer School* emerged—first imagined during a collaborative workshop at the first ArtIA Symposium. The workshop gathered artists, researchers, educators, and technologists to reflect on the tensions and possibilities around training in AI for artistic contexts. Concrete needs that surfaced included:

- **Integrating Critical Literacy:** Training should move beyond technical skills to include the deconstruction of dominant narratives, awareness of technological power dynamics, and the promotion of participatory, empowering pedagogies rooted in dialogue.
- **Playful and Accessible Educational Formats:** Participants proposed creative tools such as card games, shared glossaries, and interactive visual materials to make AI education engaging, humorous, and suitable for varying levels of experience.
- **Inclusive and Modular Learning Programs:** Educational initiatives should be designed for diverse audiences—including artists, cultural organizations, and curious citizens—supporting the development of critical, sensitive, and autonomous digital literacy.
- **Sustained Support and Recognition through Communities of Practice:** Hybrid learning communities should provide peer exchange, mentorship, and continued access to tools and

resources, while hybrid recognition systems (e.g., open badges, microcredentials, and certificates) can bridge artistic autonomy with academic and institutional validation.

Objectives

The summer school is conceived as a first step toward building a long-term, interdisciplinary learning space for artists, creatives, and cultural workers. It aims to serve as a living laboratory where different sectors come together to co-learn and co-create, laying the groundwork for a future, more permanent educational program recognized within academic institutions and cultural organizations. Topics like algorithmic bias, environmental impact, misinformation, and “small data” practices will be central to the curriculum alongside hands-on exploration of creative and cultural AI tools.³³

- **Short-term objective:** The summer school pilot project represents a first step towards building a long-term, interdisciplinary learning space.
- **Medium-term objective:** Implement a certified and credited program, recognized in both academic and cultural circles.
- **Long-term objective:** Create a more permanent educational, expansive, and public-facing training program recognized both within academic institutions and cultural organizations.

Roadmap

To be implemented in Summer 2026, the summer school will be a pilot program for developing an educational training program for AI in the arts and culture. The idea builds upon similar initiatives, such as Mila’s summer school in responsible AI.³⁴

In the first year, a short-format pilot (one month) will be launched with a limited cohort drawn from a well-defined techno-creative audience. Feedback and insights from this phase will inform the development of a broader, certified program. Key challenges include securing funding (e.g., Emploi Québec, student bursaries), mobilizing infrastructures, and attracting committed experts.

- Step 1: preparation of a short program, targeting an identified techno-creative audience (segmentation by profiles/personas).

³³ For documentation see <https://praxis.encommun.io/n/bAj3BSyZQPS8-MbDAA68VHKDIDo/>

³⁴ See <https://mila.quebec/en/continuing-education/summer-school-in-responsible-ai-and-human-rights>

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

- Step 2: sending out a restricted call for participation to test the format (one-month winter school).
- Step 3: collection of qualitative and quantitative data on needs, impact, and preferred formats.

Following the initial pilot project in 2026, the ambition is to collaborate with local academic institutions to offer joint certificate programs similar to the microcredentials program offered by the School of Interactive Arts and Technology at Simon Fraser University.

Stakeholders and Governance

The pilot project will be led by a consortium of cultural and academic institutions that foster forward-thinking learning environments at the crossroads of culture, academia, and technology. Participants will include SAT and other potential key actors, such as école NAD-UQAC, Hexagram, the college centers for the transfer of technology and social practices (e.g., the Centre de développement et de recherche en intelligence artificielle), the Pôle Synthèse, and MUTEK. To ensure the right people are both organizing and participating, the summer school's structure should be supported by institutions with demonstrated expertise in similar initiatives, such as Mila or the Îlot Balmoral in Montréal. Above all, the initiative must strike a balance: specific enough to address urgent needs in the arts and creative industries, broad enough to remain relevant and replicable in future years, and consistently centred on supporting artistic agency and imagination in the age of AI.

Tentative timeline	Steps	Tasks
July–August 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Validation of the idea with partners• Project framing (duration, format, target audiences)• Discussion panel to explore the theme of the winter school and training in art and AI more broadly	<p>Coordination between ArtIA and strategic partners</p> <p>Training department of the SAT</p>

September–December 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Development of the pilot program (content, experts, locations) • Identification of funding needs • Writing of grant application documents 	<p>Support for writing and project development</p> <p>Search for funding (Emploi Québec, Bourse Perspective, etc.)</p>
January–March 2025	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Submission of funding requests • Formation of the teaching team • Selection of masterclass topics ("sushi bar" format) 	<p>Academic, cultural, and expert partners</p> <p>Logistical planning</p>
April–May 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch of the call for participation (pilot edition, by invitation or otherwise limited) • Preparation of logistics and educational materials 	<p>Communication</p> <p>Pedagogical design</p> <p>Confirmation of venues</p>
June 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of the winter school (1 month or intensive format) • Phase 1: Masterclasses • Phase 2: Mini-projects 	<p>Facilitation, mentorship, documentation</p>
July–August 2026	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Evaluation of the prototype (surveys, interviews, partner feedback) • Model adjustments for long-term implementation 	<p>Data analysis, collective feedback</p> <p>Planning for next steps (2027 edition or permanent program)</p>

Sovereign Compute: Developing Common Infrastructures for AI in Digital Creation

As AI technologies become increasingly central to digital creation, the question of who has access to the computational resources required to use or shape these tools is more urgent than ever. In the artistic and cultural sectors, access to computing power, storage, and AI infrastructures remains largely out of reach. Current options are either inaccessible (e.g., university-only clusters), financially prohibitive, or simply ill-suited to artistic workflows. Artists working with real-time performances need low-latency systems, while others training AI models require high-performance computing and secure storage. Existing infrastructures such as Calcul Québec or the Digital Research Alliance of Canada are valuable references, but they were not designed with creative practices in mind. Moreover, the dominance of large private platforms (e.g., Amazon Web Services, Google Cloud) raises serious concerns around sovereignty, sustainability, and long-term autonomy for artistic communities. Discussions at the ArtIA Symposium made it clear: we lack a shared, ethical, artist-friendly infrastructures capable of supporting AI innovation in the arts.

Community Consultations, Shared Concerns

Infrastructures was a key concern throughout the year-long ArtIA community consultation process. Emerging across the disciplinary, thematic, and project-focused working groups, key concerns regarding infrastructures included:

- **Centralization vs. decentralization:** Centralized infrastructures offer easier management and performance benefits for high-power AI tasks, while decentralized models better support diverse artistic needs and increase resilience to technological and economic disruptions.
- **Accessibility:** Balance equitable access to existing infrastructures with the development of new infrastructures, especially for independent artists, and avoid institutional gatekeeping.
- **Technological sovereignty:** Reduce dependency on corporate cloud providers by developing local alternatives and shared governance models.
- **Collective governance:** Explore digital commons frameworks to support peer-managed, equitable infrastructure governance.³⁵

³⁵ For documentation see https://praxis.encommun.io/n/ggvcJse9R_xsOpoWfalzU9h67DM/

Objectives

This project aims to build a shared compute infrastructures for digital creation—the material foundation for an AI commons. The goal is to create a collaborative ecosystem where artists, researchers, and cultural organizations can access computational resources that are modular, distributed, and governed collectively.

Four key objectives of the infrastructures project are:

1. **Assess collective and individual needs** for shared computing infrastructures—both in terms of capacity and task-specific adequacy—including use cases such as digital creation, live performance, or the archiving and storage of digital artworks. In addition, the task-dependent adequacy of centralized, decentralized, and/or localized computing infrastructures needs to be assessed.
2. **Identify and evaluate existing infrastructures** within and beyond the current ArtIA network—examining computing power, accessibility, and governance protocols—to determine whether current resources meet existing needs or whether additional infrastructures must be made accessible or developed.
3. **Develop necessary infrastructures** in unison with practical, technical, and ethical protocols that ensure fair and equitable access to shared computational infrastructures across the network.
4. **Innovate technical and communal protocols** for facilitating accessibility and communal governance rooted in collective ownership and cooperative infrastructures.

Above all, this initiative seeks to ensure that artists and cultural organizations are not just users of AI, but active agents in defining its infrastructures and values.

Roadmap

The roadmap expands upon the in-depth discussions, which began with a series of workshops and a public panel at the ArtIA Symposia and gathered representatives from cultural organizations (e.g., Sporobole, the Society for Arts and Technology), infrastructure leaders (e.g., Calcul Québec, Mila), and academic institutions (e.g., Simon Fraser University's Metacreation Lab, Concordia University's Milieux and Applied AI Institutes, Université de Montréal).

Phase 1 of the infrastructures project launched in Summer 2025, with actors gathering as an informal pilot network—a loose yet coordinated structure that links partners willing to share local machines, offer computing time, or experiment with lightweight clusters. Most importantly, this pilot network launched a petition to the Canadian government to include the arts and culture in its Sovereign AI Compute Strategy.

In practice, this pilot network began experimenting with models and practices of shared computing infrastructures, such as those pioneered by Machine Agencies (Concordia), PINQ2, and Sporobole. The network further pioneers cross-institutional artist-in-residence programs bridging between cultural organizations and academic institutions. This pilot network is set to generate first learnings surrounding a resource-sharing protocol, a governance framework, and a toolkit to encourage small-data practices and accessible documentation.

Based on this pilot, Phase 2 calls for an in-depth study of the infrastructure needs and desires of the cultural sector as well as the potentials and shortcomings of existing computing infrastructures. This study is fundamental to create an informed vision and roadmap for developing the material infrastructures necessary to support an AI Commons for Digital Creation in Québec and Canada. This study will build the basis for lobbying governments and infrastructure leaders in developing compute infrastructures for the arts and cultural institutions.

Phase 3 of the project aims to develop compute infrastructures that are lacking and to implement both the technical and community governance protocols to facilitate access and efficiency.

Stakeholders and Governance

The initial network consists of the arts organizations Sporobole and the Society for Arts and Technology and their adjacent artistic communities, infrastructure leaders including Calcul Québec and Pinq2, and academic institutions, including Simon Fraser University's Metacreation Lab, Concordia University's Milieux and Applied AI Institutes, and the Université de Montréal. The petition to amend the Canadian government's Sovereign AI Compute Strategy gained the support of more than 200 signatories representing Canadian and Québec artists, creatives, and cultural institutions.

In moving forward, ArtIA calls for alliances across sectors—linking arts funders (e.g., CALQ, CAC), research networks (e.g., Mila, IVADO), policymakers, and infrastructure leaders—to build accessible, equitable, and shared compute infrastructures for the arts and culture in Québec and Canada.

7. Conclusion

In May 2025, the Canadian government launched its Sovereign AI Compute Strategy, pledging \$2 billion to support researchers and tech corporations in ensuring Canada's competitiveness in the global AI race. None of these funds are allocated to the arts and cultural organizations. While the federal government was strategizing, cultural organizations in Québec and Canada gathered to forge a commons-based alternative to dominant industry-first approaches to the development and governance of AI. During 18 months of stakeholder consultations and participatory action research more than 200 artists, creatives, cultural workers, researchers, and technologists in Québec and Canada collectively envisioned a commons for AI in digital creation rooted in collective ownership, cooperative infrastructures, and creative reappropriation.

Underlining the urgency of centring the arts and cultural institutions in the governance of AI as a cultural technology the ArtIA network proactively launched concrete interventions. These include a plea to the federal government to include the arts and cultural institutions in its Sovereign AI Compute Strategy; a pilot network of cultural and research institutions pioneering decentralized and collectively governed compute infrastructures; the development of an artist-centric toolkit that respects cultural diversity and data sovereignty; and an AI literacy program for the arts and cultural institutions. While ArtIA and its communities pioneered these critical initiatives, stakeholder consultations showed a larger need to rethink the role of the arts and cultural institutions not as mere downstream adopters but innovators in the development, adoption, and sense-making of AI. This conclusion highlights seven key recommendations for consideration, a preview of possible intervention points both in terms of technological developments and policy initiatives, and it contextualizes ArtIA in broader transnational developments surrounding public AI and the commons.

Key Recommendations

To ensure that the cultural sector can harness AI technologies without losing autonomy, value, or cultural specificity, a proactive strategy must be adopted. While AI raises legitimate concerns, ranging from ethical risks to potential loss of control over data and creative processes, the technology and its impact highlights larger concerns around the increasing fragility of the arts and cultural sector in Québec and Canada. As with other sectors, AI highlights the economic pressures, rapid technological shifts, and evolving needs and wants of diverse publics, which necessitate a transformation of the arts

and cultural sectors. This transformation should not be driven by the same economic and industrial objectives that guide the work of both innovation-hungry governments and powerful tech corporations. It shall, rather, reflect alternative practices rooted in cultural sensitivity, cooperativism, and ethical technological development pursued by artists and the cultural sector. As such, stakeholder consultations resulted in the following seven recommendations:

Recommendations	Intended Impact
Invest in Dedicated Compute Infrastructures	Ensure long-term access to AI tools and resources governed by collective, nonextractive models.
Strengthen Sector Expertise	Equip organizations and artists with the technical, legal, and strategic skills to appropriate AI ethically and effectively.
Establish Localized AI Labs	Provide communities with spaces for R&D, experimentation, and direct access to AI infrastructures, expertise, and tools.
Adjust Funding Programs	Adjust municipal, provincial, and federal funding programs across the arts and academic sectors to allow for the development of critical infrastructures and intersectorial collaboration.
Accelerate Technological Catch-Up	Reduce the digital divide by helping artists and cultural organizations rapidly adopt and adapt homegrown AI technologies.
Promote Knowledge Sharing and Transferability	Ensure that findings and innovations are documented, accessible, and beneficial across the sector.
Forge Cross-Sector Partnerships	Foster stronger collaboration between artistic communities, cultural institutions, technology providers, academic researchers, and policymakers.

In Moving Forward

Widespread advocacy beyond the ArtIA network, addressing municipal and regional, provincial, and federal governments, the broader Québec and Canadian arts and cultural sector beyond digital creation, technological infrastructure providers both public and private, and research institutions is essential to repositioning the standing of arts and culture vis-à-vis rapid technological advancements and to advance on the seven critical recommendations.

The circulation of this report and the findings of 18 months of stakeholder consultations will present the basis for widespread advocacy activities. Based on these findings the ArtIA network is currently lobbying the federal government to include the arts and culture in its Sovereign AI Compute Strategy. On a provincial level, the first year of ArtIA was supported by Québec's Ministère de la Culture et des Communications, and discussions are underway to extend and expand the support by the Québec government for the next phase of the project. As many of the interventions proposed highlight the need for local, situated, and decentralized approaches, both in terms of software tools and hardware infrastructures, creating closer links with municipal and regional governments to address locally situated needs presents an important avenue for further exploration.

As the seven key recommendations are not limited to the digital creative sector, the findings of the report shall serve the wider field of arts and cultural institutions in Québec and Canada. The impacts of AI on the arts and culture tend to be focused on questions of copyright and artistic labour. Rooted in digital creation, where digitality is both medium and message, ArtIA and its approach to the AI commons offers an alternative, third path that critically engages with the technology, its infrastructures, and practices to paint a more differentiated picture of AI's impacts and opportunities. We believe this to be a major contribution of digital creation to the arts and culture in Québec and Canada and, as such, are aiming to expand conversations to the wider sector, including established institutions such as museums, heritage organizations, libraries, archives, cinémathèques and film institutes, artist-run centres and cultural cooperatives, performing arts institutions (theatres, concert halls, opera and dance companies), music institutions (symphonies, conservatories, contemporary ensembles), cultural centres, galleries, and festivals.

Infrastructure providers both public and private present a critical role in the development, adoption, and sense-making of AI in the arts and cultural sector in Québec and Canada. While discussion with

institutions, such as Calcul Québec, the Digital Research Alliance of Canada, and nonprofits like Pinq2, are currently underway, if and how these institutions end up supporting the arts and cultural institutions remains to be seen. The most important work to be done in terms of infrastructures is defining the concrete needs and wants of the arts and cultural sector in Québec and Canada when it comes to access and development of sovereign compute. Rather than falling into similar narratives to Silicon Valley, which demands ever more compute, ever more data, and ever more energy and resources, the AI commons presents an alternative approach in understanding the actual, not speculative, needs of the arts and cultural sector in the face of AI. More than building large-scale infrastructures, a key approach may entail developing technical and cultural protocols for governing a diverse set of decentralized infrastructures spanning public sovereign compute and localized resources housed at cultural organizations and research institutions. The relationship to private industry remains a piece of the puzzle to be defined.

Lastly, expanding intersectorial networks across Québec and Canada and transnational relationships present a key opportunity in sharing knowledge and resources across the wider cultural and digital commons. This includes forging closer alliances with initiatives like Critic-Communs in Québec and with tech cooperatives such as Communautique, Percolab Coop, Catalyse Coop, and Interface3, which are deeply embedded in the province's social economy and align digital innovation with participatory governance, cultural production, and commons-oriented values. As highlighted in section 2, the digital commons as an approach to the development and governance of AI is gathering widespread global attention. This includes the Public AI Network, which convenes actors around public-interest AI infrastructures; the Creative Commons Signals licence, which develops frameworks for ethical AI sharing; the Open Future AI Commons, which advances policy and advocacy for AI as a shared resource; and the EU project NGI Commons, whose upcoming Digital Commons Policy Summit will further articulate these debates. Emerging from the open source community, the Linux Foundation's Generative AI Commons project is likewise building an open ecosystem for generative AI at the organizational level. Beyond the Global North, fostering connections with the many commons-adjacent initiatives documented by Coding Rights is crucial, as their review of 234 organizations—including cooperatives, collectives, networks, companies, and projects across Africa, the Americas, and Europe—reveals an emerging AI commons ecosystem that offers diverse alternative visions for the development and governance of AI.

ArtIA: Building a Commons for AI in Digital Creation

By moving boldly and steadily in community, ArtIA defies the speculative hype around the development, adoption, and sociotechnical impacts of AI in developing a commons-based alternative that centers the concrete needs and wants of the arts and cultural institutions in digital creation in Québec and Canada. While the work has just begun, the concrete impacts of empowering artists, creatives, and cultural organizations by centering these not as passive recipients but as pioneers in developing more ethical, sustainable, and resilient infrastructures, technologies, and, most importantly, practices are strongly felt.

8. References

- Attard-Frost, B. (2023). Generative AI systems: Impacts on artists and creators and related gaps in the Artificial Intelligence and Data Act. *Social Science Research Network*.
<https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4468637>
- Attard-Frost, B. (2025, January 17). The death of Canada's Artificial Intelligence and Data Act: What happened, and what's next for AI regulation in Canada? *Montréal AI Ethics Institute*.
<https://Montralethics.ai/the-death-of-canadas-artificial-intelligence-and-data-act-what-happened-and-whats-next-for-ai-regulation-in-canada/>
- Audry, S. (2021). *Art in the age of machine learning*. MIT Press.
- Aufderheide, P., & Jaszi, P. (2018). *Reclaiming fair use: How to put balance back in copyright* (2nd ed.). University of Chicago Press.
- Baack, S. (2024). A critical analysis of the largest source for generative AI training data: Common Crawl. *The 2024 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency*, 2199–2208.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3630106.3659033>
- Baio, A. (2024, September 30). AI data laundering: How academic and nonprofit researchers shield tech companies from accountability. *Waxy.Org*.
<https://waxy.org/2022/09/ai-data-laundering-how-academic-and-nonprofit-researchers-shield-tech-companies-from-accountability/>
- Bannerman, S. (2016). *International copyright and access to knowledge*. Cambridge University Press.
- Barbrook, R., & Cameron, A. (1996). The Californian ideology. *Science as Culture*, 6(1), 44–72.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/09505439609526455>
- Bauer, M. W., & Schiele, B. (2024). *AI and common sense: Ambitions and frictions* (1st ed.). Routledge.
<https://doi.org/10.4324/9781032626192>
- Bellavance, G., & Fournier, M. (2004). *Rattrapage et virages: Dynamismes culturels et interventions étatiques dans le champ de production des biens culturels*. J.-M. Tremblay.
<https://doi.org/10.1522/cla.fom.rat>
- Benkler, Y. (Ed.). (2006). *The wealth of networks: How social production transforms markets and freedom*. Yale University Press.
- Bettig, R. V. (1997). The enclosure of cyberspace. *Critical Studies in Mass Communication*, 14(2), 138–157.

- Bollier, D., Helfrich, S., & Commons Strategies Group (Eds.). (2015). *Patterns of commoning*. Commons Strategies Group.
- Boyle, J. (2023). The second enclosure movement and the construction of the public domain. *Law and Contemporary Problems*, 66, 33–74.
- Brachman, R. J., & Levesque, H. J. (2023). *Machines like us: Toward AI with common sense*. MIT Press.
- Braman, S. (2012). Technology and epistemology: Information policy and desire. In G. Bolin (Ed.), *Cultural technologies*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203117354>
- Burgess, M., & De Rosa, M. (2011). *The distinct role of artist-run centres in visual arts ecology*. MDR Burgess Consultants, Canada Council for the Arts.
- Chávez-García, M. (2023). The architects of hate: Garrett Hardin and Cordelia S. May's fight for immigration restriction and eugenics in the name of the environment. *Journal of American Ethnic History*, 43(1), 88–117. <https://doi.org/10.5406/19364695.43.1.04>
- Clarke, A. E., Friese, C., & Washburn, R. (2018). *Situational analysis: Grounded theory after the interpretive turn* (2nd ed.). SAGE.
- Conseil des arts et des lettres du Québec. (n.d.). *L'art porte conseil | 30e anniversaire du Conseil des arts et des lettres du Québec*. Retrieved September 23, 2025, from <https://www.calq.gouv.qc.ca/a-propos/30-ans-du-conseil/editorial>
- Creative Commons. (2023, October 7). *Making AI Work for Creators and the Commons*. <https://creativecommons.org/2023/10/07/making-ai-work-for-creators-and-the-commons/>
- Dardot, P., & Laval, C. (2014). *Commun: Essai sur la révolution au XXIe siècle*. la Découverte.
- Dick, C., Westlake, D., & Banting, K. (2020). *Global pluralism monitor: Canada*. Global Centre for Pluralism. <https://monitor.pluralism.ca/wp-content/uploads/2023/07/GPM-Report-Canada-EN-WEB.pdf>
- Disco, C., & Kranakis, E. (Eds.). (2013). *Cosmopolitan commons: Sharing resources and risks across borders*. MIT Press.
- Drahos, P., & Braithwaite, J. (2002). *Information feudalism: Who owns the knowledge economy* (1st ed.). Taylor and Francis.
- Drott, E. (2021). Copyright, compensation, and commons in the music AI industry. *Creative Industries Journal*, 14(2), 190–207. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17510694.2020.1839702>
- Dyer-Witheford, N., Kjosen, A. M., & Steinhoff, J. (2019). *Inhuman power: Artificial intelligence and the future of capitalism*. Pluto Press.
- Ferrari, F. (2024). A progressive vision for generative AI. In *Progressive Yearbook 2024*. Foundation for European Progressive Studies (FEPS).

- <https://feps-europe.eu/wp-content/uploads/2024/01/8.-The-age-of-digital-democracy.-A-progressive-vision-for-generative-AI.pdf>
- Furukawa Marques, D., & Durand Folco, J. (2023). Omnia sunt communia: Un état des lieux des communs au Québec. *Recherches sociographiques*, 64(1), 7–27.
<https://doi.org/10.7202/1100572ar>
- Gattinger, M., & Saint-Pierre, D. (Eds.). (2011). *Les politiques culturelles provinciales et territoriales du Canada: Origines, évolutions et mises en œuvre*. Presses de l'Université Laval.
- Gilroy, P. (2003). *The black Atlantic: Modernity and double consciousness*. Harvard University Press.
- Global Coalition for Tech Justice. (2025, February 10). *Proposal to the Artificial Intelligence Action Summit*.
- Green, B. (2021). The contestation of tech ethics: A sociotechnical approach to technology ethics in practice. *Journal of Social Computing*, 2(3), 209–225. <https://doi.org/10.23919/JSC.2021.0018>
- Grohmann, R., Rocha, A. C., & Guilherme, G. (2025). Worker-led AI governance: Hollywood writers' strikes and the worker power. *Information, Communication & Society*, 1–19.
<https://doi.org/10.1080/1369118X.2025.2521375>
- Harney, S., & Moten, F. (2013). *The undercommons: Fugitive planning and black study*. Minor Compositions.
- Harvey, F. (2011, April 4). *La politique culturelle du Québec sous Georges-Émile Lapalme et après: La Révolution tranquille qui n'a pas eu lieu*. Institut national de la recherche scientifique (INRS).
<https://inrs.ca/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/COMMUNICATION-fernand-harvey-politique-culturelle-lapalme.pdf>
- Hess, C., & Ostrom, E. (Eds.). (2006). *Understanding knowledge as a commons: From theory to practice*. MIT Press. <https://doi.org/10.7551/mitpress/6980.001.0001>
- Hong, S. Y. (2024, February 1). Alignment Assembly on AI and the commons. *Open Future*.
<https://openfuture.eu/blog/alignment-assembly-on-ai-and-the-commons/>
- Huang, S., & Siddarth, D. (2023). Generative AI and the digital commons. *arXiv*.
<http://arxiv.org/abs/2303.11074>
- Hunt, R., & Lepage-Richer, T. (2024). AI and the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research. In F. McKelvey, S. Toupin, & J. Roberge (eds.), *Northern lights and silicon dreams: AI governance in Canada (2011-2022)* (pp. 74–94). Shaping AI.
<https://www.amo-oma.ca/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ORCA-CA-Policy.pdf>
- Hunter, D. (2002). Cyberspace as place, and the tragedy of the digital anticommons. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.306662>

- Jasanoff, S. (2015). Future imperfect: Science, technology, and the imaginations of modernity. In S. Jasanoff & S.-H. Kim (Eds.), *Dreamscapes of modernity: Sociotechnical imaginaries and the fabrication of power* (pp. 1–33). University of Chicago Press.
<https://doi.org/10.7208/chicago/9780226276663.001.0001>
- Jeffries, F. (2011). Communication commoning amidst the new enclosures: Reappropriating infrastructure. *Journal of Communication Inquiry*, 35(4), 349–355.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/0196859911416502>
- Jobin, A., Ienca, M., & Vayena, E. (2019). The global landscape of AI ethics guidelines. *Nature Machine Intelligence*, 389–399. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42256-019-0088-2>
- Johnson, M. (2022). Two “Two Ostrom” problems. *History of Political Economy*, 54(S1), 69–96.
<https://doi.org/10.1215/00182702-10085629>
- Keller, P., & Tarkowski, A. (2021). The paradox of open. *Open Future*.
<https://openfuture.pubpub.org/pub/paradox-of-open/release/1>
- Kung, J., Boskovic, G., & Stix, C. (2024). *Building an AI world: Report on national and regional AI strategies*. CIFAR.
- La Coopérative de développement régional du Québec (CDRQ). (2023a, June 19). *Understanding the different types of cooperatives*. CDRQ. [https://cdrq.coop/wp/Understanding the Different Types of Cooperatives](https://cdrq.coop/wp/Understanding%20the%20Different%20Types%20of%20Cooperatives)
- La Coopérative de développement régional du Québec (CDRQ). (2023b, June 20). *Les coops en chiffres*. CDRQ. [https://cdrq.coop/wp/Les coops en chiffres](https://cdrq.coop/wp/Les%20coops%20en%20chiffres)
- Lechat, C., & Jay, D. O. (2023). *Getting our tech together: Montréal's growing community of IT cooperatives*. SEIZE.
https://www.solidarityeconomy.ca/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/V3_EN_Tech-Coop-Report.pdf
- Lévesque, B. (2008). *Le modèle Québécois d'économie sociale et solidaire: Innovations et limites*. Centre de recherche sur les innovations sociales (CRISES), ENAP–UQAM.
- LF AI & Data. (2023, September 21). *LF AI & Data launches Generative AI Commons*.
<https://lfaiadata.foundation/blog/2023/09/21/lf-ai-data-launches-generative-ai-commons/>
- Liesenfeld, A., Lopez, A., & Dingemans, M. (2023). Opening up ChatGPT: Tracking openness, transparency, and accountability in instruction-tuned text generators. *Proceedings of the 5th International Conference on Conversational User Interfaces*, 1–6.
<https://doi.org/10.1145/3571884.3604316>
- Linebaugh, P. (2014). *Stop, thief! The commons, enclosures and resistance*. PM.

- Linebaugh, P. (2021). *Red round globe hot burning: A tale at the crossroads of commons and closure, of love and terror, of race and class, and of Kate and Ned Despard*. University of California Press.
- Luciani, A. (2011). La recherche dans le domaine des arts et de la création artistique. *ACROE-ICA*.
- Macpherson, I. (2015). *Co-operative movement*. The Canadian Encyclopedia. Retrieved October 10, 2025, from <https://thecanadianencyclopedia.ca/en/article/co-operative-movement>
- Mager, A., & Katzenbach, C. (2021). Future imaginaries in the making and governing of digital technology: Multiple, contested, commodified. *New Media & Society*, 23(2), 223–236. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1461444820929321>
- Martin, R. (2013). Public and common(s). *Places Journal*, January 2013. <https://doi.org/10.22269/130124>
- McKelvey, F., Toupin, S., & Jones, M. (2024). Introduction. In F. McKelvey, S. Toupin, & J. Roberge (eds.), *Northern lights and silicon dreams: AI governance in Canada (2011–2022)* (pp. 7–30). Shaping AI. <https://www.amo-oma.ca/wp-content/uploads/2024/04/ORCA-Policy.pdf>
- MLCommons. (n.d.). *About*. Retrieved September 17, 2025, from <https://mlcommons.org/about-us/>
- Montréal International. (2024). *Intelligence artificielle | Montréal, leader mondial*. <https://www.Montréalinternational.com/fr/secteurs-cles/intelligence-artificielle/>
- Moore, S. A. (2025, May 14). *Governing the scholarly AI Commons*. Open Future. <https://openfuture.eu/publication/governing-the-scholarly-ai-commons>
- O'Mara, M. (2024). Silicon politics, from Puritan soil to California dreaming. *New England Quarterly*, 97(1), 83–97. https://doi.org/10.1162/tneq_a_01013
- Ostrom, E. (2000). Reformulating the commons. *Swiss Political Science Review*, 6(1), 29–52. <https://doi.org/10.1002/j.1662-6370.2000.tb00285.x>
- Ostrom, E. (2012). *Governing the commons: The evolution of institutions for collective action*. Cambridge University Press.
- Oxford English Dictionary. (2024). *Commons, n.* (3rd ed.). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/OED/8638487086>
- Papadopoulos, D. (2010). Insurgent posthumanism. *Ephemera: Theory & Politics in Organization*, 10(2), 134–151.
- Peszkowska, A. (2024). *AI and the commons: The paradox of open (for business)*. Open Future. <https://openfuture.eu/blog/ai-and-the-commons-the-paradox-of-open-for-business>
- Radu, R. (2021). Steering the governance of artificial intelligence: National strategies in perspective. *Policy and Society*, 40(2), 178–193. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14494035.2021.1929728>

- Saint-Pierre, D. (2007). *Politiques culturelles et patrimoines au Québec et au Canada*.
<https://doi.org/10.3406/pumus.2007.1430>
- Sengupta, U. (2015). Indigenous cooperatives in Canada: The complex relationship between cooperatives, community economic development, colonization, and culture. *Journal of Entrepreneurial and Organizational Diversity*, 4(1), 121–152.
<https://doi.org/10.5947/jeod.2015.007>
- Senneville–Robert, M. (2021). *Reconfiguration des liens de collaboration entre acteurs industriels et universitaires de la recherche en intelligence artificielle à Montréal et à Toronto*. [Masters, Maîtrise en études urbaines]. <https://espace.inrs.ca/id/eprint/11509/>
- Simpson, L. (2017). *As we have always done: Indigenous freedom through radical resistance*. University of Minnesota Press.
- Singh, N. (2017). Becoming a commoner: The commons as sites for affective socio–nature encounters and co-becomings. *Ephemera: Theory and Politics in Organisation*, 17(4), 751–776.
- Smith, S. E. K., & Couture Gagnon, A. (2024). Québec on the world stage: Examining a provincial approach to cultural diplomacy. *Journal of Arts Management, Law, and Society*, 54(6), 348–363. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10632921.2024.2442954>
- Stark, L., Greene, D., & Hoffmann, A. L. (2021). Critical perspectives on governance mechanisms for AI/ML systems. In J. Roberge & M. Castelle (Eds.), *The cultural life of machine learning* (pp. 257–280). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-56286-1_9
- Tarkowski, A. (2023). *AI and the commons: The Wikimedia movement*. Open Future.
<https://openfuture.eu/blog/ai-and-the-commons-the-wikimedia-movement>
- Tarkowski, A., & Peszkowska, A. (2024). *Common corpus: Building AI as commons*. Open Future.
<https://openfuture.eu/blog/common-corpus-building-ai-as-commons>
- Télé-Québec. (n.d.). *Histoire—Télé-Québec*. Retrieved September 23, 2025, from
<https://entreprise.teleQuebec.tv/qui-sommes-nous/histoire>
- Tello-Rozas, S., Bouchard, M. J., Lévesque, B., Brisebois, É., Courtemanche, M., Lachapelle, M. D., Rijpens, J., & Roy, H. (2025). *Social economy cluster in Québec: A tradition of solidarity oriented toward the future*. CRISES – Centre de recherche sur les innovations sociales, ENAP–UQAM.
<https://crises.uqam.ca/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/Economie-sociale-va.pdf>
- Thomas, S., & Liveley, G. (2020). Homer’s intelligent machines: AI in antiquity. In S. Cave, K. Dihal, & S. Dillon (Eds.), *AI narratives: A history of imaginative thinking about intelligent machines* (1st ed.). Oxford University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1093/oso/9780198846666.001.0001>

- Tola, M. (2015). Commoning with/in the Earth: Hardt, Negri and feminist natures. *Theory & Event*, 18(4).
<https://muse.jhu.edu/pub/1/article/595841>
- Tsing, A. L. (2021). *The mushroom at the end of the world: On the possibility of life in capitalist ruins*. Princeton University Press.
- Van Der Vlist, F., Helmond, A., & Ferrari, F. (2024). Big AI: Cloud infrastructure dependence and the industrialisation of artificial intelligence. *Big Data & Society*, 11(1), 20539517241232630.
<https://doi.org/10.1177/20539517241232630>
- Varon, J., Costanza-Chock, S., Tamari, M., Taye, B., & Koetz, V. (2024). *AI commons: Nourishing alternatives to Big Tech monoculture*. Coding Rights. <https://codingrights.org/docs/AICommons.pdf>
- Watiktinnakorn, C., Seesai, J., & Kerdvibulvech, C. (2023). Blurring the lines: How AI is redefining artistic ownership and copyright. *Discover Artificial Intelligence*, 3(1), 1–10.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s44163-023-00088-y>
- Wehbe, E. (2024, October 10). Montréal as a technological hub: The impact of diversity and immigration on innovation and global reach in a cosmopolitan core. *New Lines Institute*.
<https://newlinesinstitute.org/strategic-technology/Montréal-as-a-technological-hub-the-impact-of-diversity-and-immigration-on-innovation-and-global-reach-in-a-cosmopolitan-core/>
- Widder, D. G., West, S., & Whittaker, M. (2023). Open (for business): Big Tech, concentrated power, and the political economy of open AI. *SSRN Electronic Journal*. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4543807>
- Widder, D. G., Whittaker, M., & West, S. M. (2024). Why ‘open’ AI systems are actually closed, and why this matters. *Nature*, 635(8040), 827–833. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-024-08141-1>
- Yu, S., & Rizvi, S. J. R. (2025). *The 2024 top co-op issues survey report*. Canadian Centre for the Study of Co-operatives.
<https://usaskstudies.coop/documents/research-reports/2024-top-co-op-issues-survey-report.pdf>

9. Appendix

Appendix I: Critical Commons

- a. [Situational Mapping](#)
- b. [Original Position Paper](#)

Appendix II: [List of Projects](#)

Appendix III: [List of Tools](#)

Appendix IV: [List of Participants](#)

Appendix V: Symposium Programs

- a. [Symposium 1](#)
- b. [Symposium 2](#)
- c. [Symposium 3](#)